

Review Article

G-D's Physics' New "Order of Time"!

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Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a major "Paradigmatic Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm of General Relativity Theory (GRT) & Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Physics, based on its proven capacity to: a) resolve the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM; b) offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the otherwise unexplained "Hubble's Tension" (increase in the universe's expansion rate); and most significantly: c) Identify- and empirically validate- two (unique) "G-D's Physics" "Critical Predictions" as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's GRT & QM, i.e., relating to "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH), and "G-D's Physics" predicted "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings. "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm is based on the discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels (four basic Physical Features), thereby producing an extremely rapid series (e.g., $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) of "Universal Frames" (UF's) of the entire physical universe (at every minimal time-point)! This New "ACC" Paradigm negates the possibility of any direct (or indirect) "material-causal" (relativistic or quantum) physical interaction/s, thereby challenging (and in fact negating) GRT's "Big-Bang" Model due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)!? Instead "G-D's Physics" empirically validated "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) at the "Jewish Rosh Hashana" (JRH) due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) at that singular UCP points at annual increase in the UCP's computed rate of the universe's expansion, thereby explaining the "Hubble's Tension" – and also stipulating a different Chronological Age for the universe: 5785 Years!? An International Contest for further empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" new Age of the universe is being called for (with an additional testable unique "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" hypothesizing that the universe's time value is being accelerated (annually)!?

Note: Dr. Bentovish has been affiliated with Zefat Academic Center and Ariel University. He is now calling the leading Astronomers and Cosmologists in the world to collaborate with him to further validate the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm. Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com

Introduction

Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics has reached a "critical pivotal turning-point" akin to Einstein's revolutionizing of Twentieth Century Physics, i.e., with his discovery (and subsequent empirical validation) of "General Relativity Theory" (GRT); which was validated through Eddington's (famous) Astronomical measurement of Einstein's (unique) "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's ("double-valued") perihelion's curvature around the Sun (during the 1919 Solar Eclipse), found to be more valid than the corresponding prediction of the (preceding) "Newtonian Classical Mechanics" Paradigm; This is based on the well-known Philosopher of Science, Thomas Kuhn's, famous analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" (in 1962), in which he discovered that the development in any given scientific discipline alternates between phases of "Standard Science", e.g., in which the scientific inquiry (within that given discipline) is based on certain assumptions (and laws) – which eventually reaches the limits of its "usefulness", thereby leading to the appearance of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of that Old "Standard Paradigm; Such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of that "Old Standard Paradigm" (OSP) is signified by the appearance

of an (intrinsic) "theoretical-inconsistency" found within the "pillars" of that "OSP", as well as a principle inability of that OSP to explain a certain key empirical finding (or phenomenon) which cannot be explained based on that OSP!? According to Kuhn's (well-accepted) analysis, the appearance of such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" inevitably leads to the discovery of a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) which must satisfy a set of "stringent scientific criteria" in order for it to be accepted as the New "Standard Paradigm", which must include:

- Resolution of the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between the "pillars" of the Old Standard Paradigm (ISP).
- A satisfactory explanation of the (otherwise) "unexplained" empirical phenomenon (which could not be explained by the OSP).
- Most importantly, the identification of at least one (unique) "Critical Prediction" predicted by this NSP, which differentiates it from the corresponding predictions of the OSP – which, when empirically validated (as more valid than the OSP's corresponding predictions) is inevitably "crowned" as the New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) within that given scientific discipline!

Indeed, when these "stringent scientific criteria" are satisfactorily met by the NSP, a (major) "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the OSP to the NSP takes place, which then becomes the New "Standard Paradigm" for that given scientific discipline! The reason for the equivalence of the current "Paradigmatic-Crisis" occurring in Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics – to the major scientific revolution brought about by Einstein's GRT, is that now (as then) there appears:

- a) A basic "theoretical-inconsistency" between the "pillars" of Einstein's GRT (e.g., dealing with the "macroscopic-large" universe) and Quantum Mechanics (QM, attuned to the "microscopic-subatomic" universe).
- b) A principle inability of the OSP (called: the "Material-Causal" Paradigm, as will explained) to explain a major (otherwise "unexplained") phenomenon, e.g., the accelerated expansion of the universe – specifically: "Hubble's Tension", i.e., the otherwise "unexplained" increase in the universe's measured rate of expansion – from its "early Cosmological" measured rate of expansion to the "current-Astronomical" increased measured rate of the universe's expansion!
- c) The emergence of a (candidate) NSP currently termed: "G-D's Physics" which identified at least two (unique) "Critical Predictions" that differentiate it from the corresponding predictions of the OSP – which are being empirically validated in the current article, thereby leading to the unequivocal acceptance of this NSP: "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) for Twenty-First Century Physics.

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the new "G-D'S PHYSICS" Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-D'S PHYSICS" identified two unique "Critical-Prediction" relating to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" (New Year's) time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCP; According to the Old ("Material-Causal") GRT's Paradigm, the (purely hypothetical concept of) DM predicts a "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion – i.e., which should not increase over time! In contrast, according to one of the new Theoretical Postulates of the "G-D'S PHYSICS" termed: "The Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH), whenever there is a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), e.g., of a large group of human-beings focusing upon this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), this results in an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" ("UNCIARE")! For example, during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana's" (new year) two days' special time-interval, according to the CUFT (unique) "UNCIARE-JRH" "Critical Prediction", there should be measured a "non-continuous increase" in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., predicted to occur during the JRH's two days special annual interval of a CHCF!)

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl et al.[27-29] set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \Sigma\{O\{i-o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)]= O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF\{i\dots n\}\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given

object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Confirmation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction

In order to confirm "G-D's Physics" (unique) "UNCIARE (JRH)" Critical Prediction it is necessary to gauge and compare the rate of the universe's expansion – at it's early (Cosmological) stages, as opposed to the current (Astronomical) measure of the universe's rate of expansion: Once again, according to "G-D's Physics" (unique) UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction, the rate of the universe's expansion increases at every year's JRH's CHCF (two days' special time interval – e.g., at which Millions of Jew collectively focus on this singular higher-ordered UCP!), hence predicted to lead to an overall increase in the rate of the universe's expansion from its early Cosmological measure to the current Astronomical measure of the universe's expansion rate! (As indicated above, this unique "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction predicting an overall increase in the universe's expansion rate from its early Cosmological to the current Astronomical rate of expansion – stands in stark contrast to the Old MCR's GRT's purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" prediction regarding the rate of the universe's expansion which should remain **constant over time!**?)

Indeed, the "Hubble's Tension"[34]- empirical findings (unequivocally) supports "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH prediction regarding such an increase in the rate of the universe's expansion – from the universe's initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [34-40]?! In other words, "G-D's Physics" unique UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction, predicting that the Universe's expansion rate will increase (annually) during every consecutive JRH's two days' (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – is validated by the "Hubble's Tension"[34-40] findings! In contrast, these "Hubble's Tension"[34-40] findings cannot be explained by the current "Standard Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT, which assumes that the universe's accelerated expansion is the result of (purely hypothetical) "Dark Matter" concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe (but which failed to be detected despite twenty years of intensive experimentation attempting to do so)!? Even beyond that, even theoretically this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept could not account for the empirically observed "Hubble's Tension"[34-40] because such a (purely hypothetical) DM concept could only account for a constant-rate expansion of the universe (e.g., over time), but not for the "Hubble's Tension"[32,33,40] results indicating that the universe's rate of expansion increases over time, which precisely confirm "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction!

Likewise, the empirically measured "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings precisely support "G-D's Physics" novel UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given particle as function of its "Object Spatial Consistency" (across a series of UF's Frames); therefore the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the (relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen") than the (relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen") was predicted by "G-D's Physics" to lead to a "spatially-smaller" - and spatially more accurate" - measurement of that "Muon-Hydrogen" empirical findings! In contrast, these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" empirical findings could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite var-

ious attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force"[49], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction [53,57], higher dimension gravity [48], a new boson [52], and the quasi-free hypothesis $\pi+51$; and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm! Hence, these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" empirical results unequivocally support "G-D's Physics" unique Critical Prediction stemming from its (novel) UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given (subatomic) particle (or relativistic object)!

Discussion

Based on the unequivocal empirical validation of two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Scientific Paradigm (OSP), "G-D's Physics" is being "crowned" as the New Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! Several quite far-reaching theoretical conclusions ensue from this acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm:

"G-D's Physics" A-Causal Computation Paradigm

One of the profound new insights (and theoretical implications) of "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm is its "A-Causal Computation" characteristics; Contrary to the Old "Material-Causal Random" OSP underlying (Twentieth Century's) GRT & QM, which assumed that the whole origination- dynamics- and evolution- of the entire physical universe can be explained merely based on direct (or even indirect) "material-causal random" physical interactions between certain ("macroscopic-relativistic" or "microscopic-quantum") material entities (e.g., including GRT's "Big-Bang" Model which assumes that the universe's creation can be explained based on an initially assumed "nuclear explosion", which created all of the galaxies, mass and energy in the universe, as will be delineated subsequently); The New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm discovered the existence of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "time", "energy" and "mass") – thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames", i.e., comprising all of the universe's exhaustive spatial pixels at each (such) "minimal time-point"! "G-D's Physics" computed rate of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP of this (extremely rapid) series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) is derived from the newly discovered "Universal Computational Formula" (below):

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...x} [Px] (a...z)

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

Wherein the UCP represented by the Hebrew Letter " ך " computes at an extremely rapid rate, e.g., of " c^2/h " = 1.36^{50} (sec) simultaneously every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising every consecutive UF's – including the UCP's complete integration of those Four basic Physical Features through the UCF's: $s * e / t * m$ computation (e.g., for each exhaustive spatial pixel – from "a to z")!

According to this New UCF, the rate at which this singular (higher-ordered) UCP computes this (extremely rapid) series of UF's is " c^2/h " = 1.36^{50} sec! which means many-many "trillions" of times each second! This means that at each and every such "trillionth" of a second a new Universal Frame (UF) is being "simultaneously" computed by this UCP – for all of the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe! But since this UCP "simultaneously" computes all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe, then "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm also represents an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, i.e., implying that there cannot exist any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (in the universe) existing either in the same- or different-UF's frame/s! This is simply because if this singular (higher-ordered) UCP "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s – then there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" (or even "different" UF's frame/s)!

The "Cinematic-Film Metaphor's" "A-Causal Computation" Demonstration

A simple (yet elegant) demonstration of "G-D's Physics" new "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm's negation of the (very) possibility of the existence of any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or even "different" UF's frame/s is given based on a "Cinematic-Film Metaphor": Imagine a "cinematic-film scenario" which depicts a (heavy) "Mercury-Ball" impacting a "Glass-Jar" (filled with water), leading to the breakage of this "Glass-Jar" and consequent "water-spillage"; we can use this simple "cinematic-film scenario" to demonstrate "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm: if we pose the simple question: what "caused" the "breakage" of this "Glass-Jar" (and consequent "water-spillage")? The apparently "obvious" answer would be that it was the "impact" of the (heavy) "Mercury-Ball" which "caused" this "breakage" of the "Glass-Jar" (and consequent "water-spillage"). But, if we closely examine this "Cinematic Film Metaphor", specifically the possibility of the existence of any such "material-causal" physical interactions between those (heavy) "Mercury-Ball" and (water-filled) "Glass-Jar" – in any (single or multiple) cinematic "film-frame/s"? we would find that there cannot (in principle) exist any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between these "Mercury-Ball" and "Glass-Jar" in any single or multiple film-frame/s! This is due to the (simple) fact, that since in each of the consecutive film-frames (comprising this brief film-scenario) both the "Mercury-Ball" and "Glass-Jar" are being presented "simultaneously" – there cannot exist any such "cause-and-effect" (e.g., "material-causal") physical interaction/s between those two objects. Since both the "Mercury-Ball" and the "Glass-Jar" appear "simultaneously" – in each of the consecutive film-frames (comprising this brief "film-scenario"), there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between them, at least in none of the (single or multiple) film-frame/s comprising this film-scenario! Likewise, there cannot exist any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between these "Mercury-Ball" and "Glass-Jar" objects – also "in-between" any two consecutive (or even "non-consecutive") film-frame/s, since there is no "transference" of any "material-entity" or "force" across any two such (consecutive or even non-consecutive) film-frame/s (e.g., being "separated" by a pure beam of light shining "in-between" any two consecutive film-frames)!? So, we reach the inevitable conclusion that from the (strict)

perspective of this "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" (i.e., "film-scenario), there cannot exist any such "material-causal" physical interactions between these two "Mercury-Ball" and "Glass-Jar" objects – existing either in any (single or multiple) "film-frame/s", or (even) "in-between" any two such (consecutive or non-consecutive) film-frames!?

So (then) what gives us the "impression" (or "perception") of the existence of the (seemingly "obvious") "material-causal" (e.g., "cause-and-effect") physical interactions that seem to exist between the "impact" of that (heavy) "Mercury Ball" (on the "fragile water-filled") "Glass-Jar" – which seems to "cause" the "breakage" of the "Glass-Jar" (and consequent "water-spillage")? Well, it is the "arrangement" of those "film-frames" (scenario) in that particular "order", e.g., in which the "proximity" between this "Mercury-Ball" and that "Glass-Jar" increases (across a given series of "film-frames") leading to their "conjoining" (in a particular film-frame), which is followed by the depiction of the "breakage" of the "Glass-Jar" (and "spillage" of its water content!) which gives us the "impression" (or "perception") of the existence of such "cause-and-effect" ("material-causal") physical interactions between the "Mercury-Ball's" (impact) and the "Glass-Jar's" (breakage)!? What can we infer from this "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" and "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm? Simply put, we understand that even through (in this "cinematic-film scenario") it seems that there exist a "cause-and-effect" ("material-causal") physical interaction/s between the "Mercury-Ball's" (impact) & "Glass-Jar's" (breakage) – in truth, there cannot (really) exist any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between these two objects (e.g., either in any single/multiple "film-frames", or indeed even "in-between" them!?) Rather, what gives us the "impression/perception" of the existence of such "cause-and-effect" ("material-causal") physical interactions between these two ("Mercury-Ball" & "Glass-Jar") physical objects is the particular "arrangement" of the film-frame's "proximity" (e.g., between these two "objects", and consequent "breakage" of the "Glass-Jar" and subsequent "water-spillage" etc.)!? So, we can see through this (particular) "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" that what seems as the existence of a (simple) "material-causal" (e.g., "cause-and-effect") physical relationships between two objects ("Mercury-Ball" impact and "Glass-Jar" breakage) – in truth, represents an "A-Causal Computation" arrangement of those "cinematic-film frames" (by the "Producer" of the film) in a particular "order" which gives us the impression of the existence of (particular) "material-causal" physical interactions between these (two) objects!?

"G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm

Indeed, based on this (simple) "Cinematic-Film Metaphor we can begin understanding "G-D Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm; This is because alike this Cinematic-Film Metaphor's (above) negation of the very possibility of the existence of any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between the two objects (e.g., "Glass-Jar" and "Mercury-Ball") either in any (single or multiple) "film-frame", or indeed across any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive) "film-frame/s"; "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm asserts that there cannot exist any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single or multiple "Universal Frame/s" (e.g., constituting the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point") – due to the "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle's" (UCP's) "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and "in-between" any two (such) consecutive UF's frame/s, all of those exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s) "dissolve" back into the singularity of the UCP! So that due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s there cannot exist any "material-causal" (e.g., "cause-and-effect") physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's

frame/s! Nor can there exist any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – across any two consecutive (or even non-consecutive) UF's frame/s, due to the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

"G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation's" Negation of the Big-Bang Model!

Indeed, based on this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (for Twenty-First Century's Physics), it has been shown that this New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm negates the Old Material-Causal Random's (MCR's) GRT's "Big-Bang" Model! This is because, according to this Old MCR's GRT Model the entire physical universe has been created by an initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion which "caused" the creation of all of the Suns, Galaxies, mass and energy etc. in the universe; This means that according to this Old MCR's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model, the entire physical universe was created by a "first" UF's "Big-Bang" "nuclear explosion" – that "caused" the creation of all the Suns, Galaxies, "matter" and "energy" in the "second", "third", "fourth"... "Nth" UF's frame/s! But, as we've already seen, according to "G-D's Physics" (novel) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" ("cause-and-effect") physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or even "different" (consecutive or non-consecutive) UF's frame/s! This is due to the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s – including the "first", "second", "third", etc. "Nth", so that there cannot exist any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between the assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion and its assumed "creation" of any Suns, Galaxies, "matter", "energy" etc.; either in the "first", "second", "third" etc. UF's frame/s; Nor can there exist any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in this "first" assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion – and any of the exhaustive spatial pixels in any of the subsequent: "second", "third", "fourth", etc. ... "Nth" UF's frame/s! This is because all of the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising that "first" (assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion – must "dissolve" back into the singularity of the higher-ordered UCP "in-between" that "first" and "second" (or "third", "fourth" etc.) UF's frame/s, so that there cannot exist any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between such an assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion and any (subsequently assumed) creation of "Suns", "Galaxies", "matter" or "energy" etc. in any subsequent UF's frame/s!

Instead, what truly exist, e.g., according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm is merely a series of UF's frames – all consecutively produced by this singular higher-ordered UCP, which describe an accelerated expanded physical universe! Indeed, due to "G-D's Physics" (empirically validated) New Scientific Paradigm's assertion that the entire physical universe (e.g., including all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) is continuously "computed"- "dissolved"- "re-computed"- and "developed"- at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!" (i.e., many "trillions" of times each second!) we cannot (any longer) explain the "origination", "sustenance" or "development" of the entire physical universe is the result of any (initially assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion; nor its accelerated rate of expansion can be explained through the Old MCR's GRT's assumed existence of a purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (e.g., "DM", assumed to comprise up to 95% of the matter in the universe- but which could not be detected for the past two full decades, despite numerous experimental attempts to do so)?! This is because, once again, this Old MCR's "DM" (purely hypothetical) concept is assumed to "cause" the "expulsion" of certain outer galactic elements!? But, once again, "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm strictly negates the very possibility of the existence of any such "material-causal" ("cause-and-effect") physical interactions between any such (purely hypothetical) "DM" and any such

"outer galactic elements" – i.e., due to the (abovementioned) "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s)! In fact, "G-D's Physics" principle negation of the Old MCR's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model for the whole creation, sustenance and development of the entire physical universe has been analyzed and proven based on "G-D's Physics" (novel) discovered "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP, below).

"G-D's Physics" New "Time" Definition & "Universal Consciousness Reality"!

Contrary to the Old Material-Causal Paradigm's conception of "time" – which is defined based on certain (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between a given relativistic observer and relativistic object (or phenomenon), or between a certain subatomic probe element and a corresponding target's "probability wave function" (e.g., which causes the "collapse" of that "probability wave function" into a singular complimentary "energy-space" or "time-mass" value); The New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm defines "time" in a completely different "order-dependent" manner! Based on "G-D's Physics" (novel) "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm's recognition that due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel's (four basic Physical Features of "space", "energy" "mass" and "time"), e.g., comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s; and based on "G-D's Physics" strict negation of the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s, we begin realizing that the true nature of "time" stems from the UCP's (singular higher-ordered) computation of the "degree of change" (i.e., "Object-inconsistent") pertaining to any given object (at any given exhaustive spatial pixel – across a series of UF's frame/s)! However, since this singular higher-ordered UCP's computation of the "time" value of any given "object" – stems from the UCP's consecutive computation of the series of UF's frame/s; and since "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s all such "object/s" and all exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP (e.g., but there doesn't exist any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s); "time" does not exist "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

Once again, "G-D's Physics" strict (novel) computational definition of "time" is given as the UCP's computation of an "Object-inconsistent" changes computed by the UCP (for any given object) across a series of UF's frame/s:

Based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Scientific Paradigm, i.e., which negates the (very) possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., existing in the "same"- or even "different"- UF's frame/s); "G-D's Physics" novel Computational Definition of the concept of "time" – significantly differs from "material-causal" definitions of "time", according to both GRT & QM! This is because, according to GRT, the concept of time is defined relative to the Speed of a Light signal transmitted from a specific "event" (or "entity" or "phenomenon"); This is the reason that GRT points at the dependency of the "temporal value" of any such given "event" (or "phenomenon") – on the velocity of the relativistic observer, relative to three Speed of Light (SOL). This is simply because if we were to take two: "slow" and "fast" relativistic observers – travelling away from a given "mine-explosion", each one of them would measure the "temporal value" of the occurrence of this "mine-explosion" differently; because it would take the same Light signal longer to reach the "slower" relativistic observer than the "faster" relativistic observer: Hence, the "slower" relativistic observer would necessarily measure a "higher-temporal value" for the occurrence of this "mine-explosion", than the "faster" relativistic

observer! Moreover, as Relativity Theory teaches us, this "material-causal" dependency of the measurement values of that "mine-explosion" – on the velocity of the observer, i.e., relative to the SOL – also extends to the "spatial localization" of that "explosion"; which led to Relativity's unification of the "spatial" and "temporal" (apparently "separate" dimensions) into a "four-dimensional" "Space-Time" continuum!

Likewise, Quantum Mechanics' (QM's) definition of "time" is also dependent upon the "material-causal" (and also "random": e.g., MCR) direct physical interaction between two given subatomic "probe" and "target" elements: wherein it is assumed that it is the direct "material-causal" physical interaction between any given (subatomic) "probe" and "target's" "probability wave function" – that "causes" the "collapse" of this (assumed) "target's" probability wave-function into a singular "complimentary" "time-mass" or "space-energy" value/s?! Indeed, Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle directly addresses this "material-causal" dependency of the accuracy measurement level of the subatomic "probe" element – as determining (or "causing") the accuracy level of the "complimentary" "target's collapsed" value?! Indeed, the (widely accepted) probabilistic interpretation of QM precisely explains this (latter) "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle" (HUB) as the result of this (direct) "material-causal" (random) physical interaction between the "probe" and "target's" probability wave-function" (subatomic) elements – which "causes" the "collapse" of the "target's" probability wave function into the singular "complimentary": "time-mass" or "energy-space" value/s!? This direct "material-causal interdependency" of (for instance) the "energy" and "space" "complimentary" Physical Features, is perhaps more "intuitive" (or "understandable" to us), because we can comprehend that if we increase (for example) the "energy" value of the subatomic "probe" element, then its "energetic-impact" upon the other (subatomic) "target's" probability wave-function" will be "greater" – therefore, "causing" a greater "alteration" in the accuracy level of this (latter "collapsed") subatomic "target" element, e.g., indicating HUP! In contrast, since we do not have any direct "intuitive sense" of the "complimentary" relationship/s that may exist between the two Physical Features of "time" and "mass"; we find it relatively "difficult" to comprehend the "time-mass" complimentary measurement accuracy level/s?! (Interestingly, as will be shown below, "G-D's Physics" novel UCP's computational definitions of "time" and "mass" sheds a completely new light and understanding regarding the "intrinsic-computational complementarity" of these two "HUB's complimentary pair");

So, we can see that the Old MCR Paradigm's: GRT's & QM's conception of the "time" value of any given "event"/"phenomenon" (etc.), which are based upon the direct "material-causal" physical interaction/s between (such) a relativistic "event" and a relativistic observer, or between a subatomic "probe" and corresponding "target" elements – are strictly negated by the New "G-D's Physics" ACC Scientific Paradigm; based on the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' (Four basic Physical Features – i.e., including "time"!), which therefore negates the (very) possibility of the existence of any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions! In contrast, "G-D's Physics" new computational definition of "Time" is based on the UCP's computation of any given (relativistic or quantum) "object's" "Object-inconsistent" presentations:

"Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] \neq O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\} \text{ such that: } T: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - On\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

This means, that in contrast to the Old MCR's GRT's & QM's "material-causal" conception of the "temporal-value" of any given "event" (or "phenomenon" etc.), "G-D's Physics" New ACC Paradigm's UCP's computational definition of "time" – totally depends upon the UCP's "Object-inconsistent" (abovementioned) computation (e.g., of the degree of "change" that has occurred in that particular "object" across a series of UF's frame/s)! But, since the UCP's computation of any given "Object-inconsistent" "time" value is carried out "simultaneously" with the UCP's computation of the other (three) Physical Features, e.g., of "space", "energy" and "mass", therefore, we can only look at the UCP's computation of the "time" value of any given event – as it is "intertwined" with the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of the other (three) Physical Features, e.g., of "space", "energy" and "mass", which are all unified within the UCP's (novel) "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF, see Figure 2):

"G-D's Physics" Complete Integration of GRT-QM & the Four Physical Features!

Indeed, "G-D's Physics" discovery of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' Four (basic) Physical Features, has also led to its discovery of a singular unified "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) which completely integrates between those Four Physical Features (i.e., as "secondary computational by-products" of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle", "UCP") (Figure 1)!

In order to see how this (novel) "G-D's Physics" Computational Definitions of each of the Four (basic) Physical Features is (fully) integrated within the UCF's singular formula – i.e., and which also allows for "G-D's Physics" complete integration of GRT & QM (as "special-cases" within the broader- exhaustive- higher-ordered theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" UCF!); let us examine "G-D's Physics" (novel) "Computational Definitions" of each of those Four (basic) Physical Features:

Indeed, "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's "Computational Definitions" of the Four Physical Features are based on the discovery of the UCP's two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"): wherein the UCP's computation of the UF's "frame" (level's) – "consistent" (e.g., "space") or "inconsistent" ("energy") Physical Features relates to the UCP's computation of the degree of "consistency" or "inconsistency" of any given "object", relative to the entire UF's ("coordinate-system", e.g., across a series of UF's frame/s)! Or, conversely, the UCP's computation of any given object's "object" (e.g., "internal-composition's) – "consistent" (e.g., "mass") or "inconsistent" (e.g., "time") produce the entire UF's exhaustive spatial pixels' Four basic Physical Features values! (See Figure 1).

The UCP's Four Physical Features (Novel) Computational Definitions

"Space"

S: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$ such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) \leq f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i..n)]$ where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i..n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure! Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location

of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the.

"Energy"

E: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$ such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i..n)]$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

"Mass"

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

M: $\Sigma[O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O_{i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(i..n)\} / h * n \{UF's(i..n)\}$ where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

M: $[O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i..n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$ Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

T: $\Sigma[O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O_{i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(i..n)\} / c * n \{UF's(i..n)\}$ such that: $T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i..n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Table 1 illustrates the UCP's Computational Dimensions' derived Four (basic) Physical Features:

Table 1: UCP's Computational Dimensions' Derivation of the Four Physical Features

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	"Space"	"Mass"
Inconsistent	"Energy"	"Time"

In order to illustrate the (full) integration of "G-D's Physics" singular "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) – not only of the Four (basic) Physical Features, but also of GRT & QM (e.g., as "special-cased" within its

UCF, as Einstein envisioned!) let us examine two derivatives of this singular UCF, i.e., of a Relativistic and Quantum Formats!

The UCF's Relativistic Format

$$\left. \begin{matrix} \text{E} * \text{s} \\ \text{t} \end{matrix} \right\} = \left. \begin{matrix} \text{M} * \text{c}^2 \\ \text{h} \end{matrix} \right\}$$

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format:

$$\left. \begin{matrix} \text{t} * \text{m} \\ \text{c}^2 \end{matrix} \right\} = \left. \begin{matrix} \text{s} * \text{e} * \text{h} \\ \text{c}^2 \end{matrix} \right\}$$

in which "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" ("complimentary pairs") are embedded as "special cases" within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of "G-D'S PHYSICS").

Interestingly, this (latter) new "G-D's Physics" UCP's (∘) computation of the UCF's "Quantum Format" clearly reveals a much "deeper" understanding of the basic "computational constraint" imposed by Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" that stems from "G-D's Physics" singular higher-ordered UCP's simultaneous computation of those Four (basic) Physical Features (for all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe) – rather than as "caused" by any (direct) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two subatomic) "probe" and "target" elements; which serves as the current QM's "theoretical explanation" for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" (e.g., and associated assumed "collapse" of the "target's probability wave-function" – as "caused" by this direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the subatomic probe and target elements)!? This is because if we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's computational definitions of these Four basic Physical Features (above) – arising from the four possible combinations of the two Computational Dimensions: "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"): "Frame" – "consistent" (e.g., "space") or "inconsistent" (e.g., "energy"), and "Object" – "consistent" (e.g., "mass") or "inconsistent" ("time")! Then, we can immediately see that the real "intrinsic computational-complimentary" reason for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" is not any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between the subatomic "probe" and "target's" (assumed "probability wave function") elements! But rather, this "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity" is the real reason for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" stems from the "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity": i.e., since the UCP simultaneously computes both the "Framework" – "consistent" ("space") and "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "con-

sistent" ("mass") and "inconsistent" ("time") values of any given object (e.g., exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – at the incredible rate of "c2/h" = 1.36-50 sec'), therefore any increase in the accuracy level of the measurement of any one of these "UCP's computational pairs", i.e., "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") necessarily leads to a proportional decrease in the other "UCP's computational pair's" accuracy level!

Moreover, since this singular (higher-ordered) UCP simultaneously computes all Four Physical Features (for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s), therefore the singular "Universal Computational Formula" completely integrates (e.g., for the first time in Physics!) those Four Physical Features as "secondary computational by-products" of the same singular (higher-ordered) UCP computation! Indeed, as can be seen from the two (abovementioned) "Relativistic" and "Quantum" Formats of this singular UCF, we can see that "G-D's Physics" novel UCF completely integrates – not only between those Four basic Physical Features, but also completely integrates GRT & QM as "special cases" within this broader and (indeed) exhaustive new theoretical framework! Hence, not only do those key Relativistic "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ("E = Mc²") and Quantum's Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" (e.g., stemming not from any direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the subatomic "probe" and "target" elements, but is rather due to the "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity"!)) being embedded within the singular UCF's Relativistic and Quantum Formats, but more broadly, it's been previously shown that all key Relativistic and Quantum phenomena and laws are being replicated (and indeed "transcended" as merely representing "special cases" within "G-D's Physics" more exhaustive theoretical framework).

"G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Related Universe's True Age!

So, we've seen that "G-D's Physics" new "Computational Definition" of "time":

"Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] \neq O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\} \text{ such that: } T: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq c * h \{ \{UF's (i\dots n) \}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Must be viewed within the broader (computational) perspective of the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of the other three Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "energy" and "mass") represented by the UCP's (abovementioned) "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF):

But, based on the current (above) Results, e.g., validating "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction", wherein the UCP's produced rate of the universe's expansion increases annually – due the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) taking place during the JRH's two days' (time interval); **an entirely new conception of the universe's overall "time-span", i.e., the "universe's age" is discovered based on "G-D's Physics" empirically validated "UNCIARE-JRH" "Critical Prediction"!**

"G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Precise & Longitudinal Measurements!

Based upon "G-D's Physics" discovery of that singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) of the entire physical universe (e.g., at every "minimal time-point" at the incredible rate of " $c2/h = 1.36\text{-}50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") Another (novel) Theoretical Postulate of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) which stipulates that whenever there exists a large group of individual human-beings such as during the two days of the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH) in which Millions of Jews (all around the world) focus on the singularity of this "UCP", then this brings about an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) – which can explain the (otherwise) "unexplained" gap that exists between the early Cosmological value of the universe's rate of expansion and the current (significantly increased) Astronomical rate of the universe's expansion, i.e., recently termed: the "Hubble's Tension"!

Hence, "G-D's Physics" alternative theoretical explanation for the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion is given through G-D's Physics "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Expansion" (UNCIARE), e.g., brought about by a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), such as during the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah's" (JRH) two days special time-interval in which Millions of Jews (all over the world) focus upon this singular (higher-ordered) UCP! Hence, the accelerated expansion of the universe's expansion rate is brought about by the JRH-CHCF, which results in a predicted "UNCIARE-JRH" annual increase in the uni-

verse's expansion rate! (e.g., rather than is the result of the "purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" [DM] concept – i.e., which is in fact negated by G-D'S Physics' NSP: a) because this purely hypothetical DM concept failed to be verified experimentally for the past two full decades?! And b) due to "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Computational Duality Principle" [CDP] which principally negates its existence, based on a computational-empirical analysis! see below). This UNCIARE-JRH annual increase in the universe's expansion rate has been calculated to comprise a "*Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ " per year; This (novel) G-D's Physics unique "Critical Prediction" of the UNCIARE-JRH's increase of an MAI (e.g., annually) opens an entirely new "window of opportunity" for the validation of the G-D'S Physics NSP – as more valid than the Old MCR Paradigm (e.g., of GRT & QM), i.e., both through: a) "Precise" MAI (sensitive) annual Astronomical measurements "during" the JRH's two days' special time-interval; B) Based on "Longitudinal" Astronomical/Cosmological measurements indicating a "cumulative" increase in the universe's expansion rate over any given "time-interval" (e.g., such as over the past 10, 50 or 100 years, or potentially much longer time-intervals, etc., as delineated below)!

Specifically, the significant increase in the universe's measured rate of expansion, i.e., from its (initial) Cosmological "Background Radiation" rate to its (current) "Astronomical" (significantly higher) rate of expansion – termed" the "Hubble's Tension"³¹⁻³⁹; precisely supports G-D's Physics' assumed "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE-JRH) "Critical Prediction", as more valid than the Old MCR's (GRT's) "constant-expansion rate" corresponding prediction (see Figure 2):

This is because, according to Old MCR's Paradigm's GRT "Big-Bang" Model, the universe's expansion rate should be "constant" – as caused by the assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event (e.g., and two additional "Exceptional Expansive Events" (or factors, EEE's; as delineated below and previously). Specifically, the (purely hypothetical) "Dark Matter" [DM] concept, which is assumed by the Old MCR Paradigm to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe (e.g., but which could not be detected experimentally for the past two decades despite numerous attempts to do so?!) – could only account for such a "constant rate" of the universe's expansion, because the quantity of this purely hypothetical DM is (itself) "constant" (e.g., or may in fact "diminish" over time, hence leading to a deceleration of the universe's expansion rate...) Hence, according to the Old MCR's GRT Model of the universe, the universe has been created 13.8 Billion years ago, and since then its expansion rate should have been "constant" (i.e., as further delineated below through this MCR's assumed three purely hypothetical EEE's). In contrast, according to the G-D's Physics (novel) Scientific Paradigm, there exists a "Universe's non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE), which is brought about through the JRH's (two days') "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) upon the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which increases the universe's rate of expansion by a Minute Annual Increase (MAI) (i.e., of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc (during the JRH's two days' time-interval!) Hence, the existence of this (specific JRH associated) CHCF is seen as "critical" for the continuous (cumulative) increase in the universe's "accelerated" expansion rate, which also points at the G-D's Physics "Six Days Creation Model" (delineated previously) highlighting the centrality of this CHCF as a key (essential and necessary) factor for the empirically observed "UNCIARE" (e.g., otherwise "unexplained") increase in the universe's expansion rate! Consequently, the G-D'S PHYSICS introduces an entirely different account of the universe's (stipulated) age (and "origin") of the physical universe, e.g., to be derived from the MAI's predicted (annual increase) in the universe's expansion rate: originated 5785 years ago!

Therefore, the current article provides initial (unequivocal) empirical support for the G-D's Physics UNCIARE's (unique) "Critical Prediction" regarding the (cumulative) MAI's increase in the universe's expansion rate – i.e., producing the otherwise ("unexplained") "Hubble's Tension"! This is (once again) because unlike GRT's "Big-Bang" Model which assumes a "constant" rate of the universe's expansion (e.g., and the universe's creation based on an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event dated 13.8 Billion years ago) – leading to an "unexplained" "Hubble's Tension" Enigma which cannot account for a significant increase in the universe's expansion rate over time; the (novel) G-D'S PHYSICS explains the universe's (continuous) "origination" by that (singular, higher-ordered) UCP, based on its continuous computation- "dissolution" "re-computation" and "evolution"- of every exhaustive spatial pixel (e.g., simultaneously), at an incredible rate of "c2/h" = 1.36-50 sec! thereby leading to the UCP's production of an incredibly rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal time-point"! Indeed, according to this (entirely new) conception of the universe's (constant and continuous) "origination"- "dissolution"- "re-computation"- and "development"- by this singular (higher-ordered) UCP; and the (abovementioned) centrality of the human CHCF (e.g., during the JRH's two days' special time-interval), which brings about an annual "MAI" increase in the UCP's rate of the universe's expansion rate – leads to the G-D's Physics (clear and unique) "Critical Prediction" of "UNCIARE", which is empirically validated- by the (otherwise "unexplained" by the Old MCR's GRT "Big-Bang Model)! Indeed, it is due to the G-D's Physics centrality of the JRH (two days') CHCF (time-interval) – and specifically the MAI's (cumulative) increase in the universe's expansion rate (over time), that the G-D's Physics stipulated age of the physical universe is only 5785 (rather than the Big-Bang Model's stipulated 13.8 Billion years!

In order to further support this (novel) G-D's Physics UCP's CHCF (JRH's) model of the universe's UNCIARE increase (over time), we highlight its (conceptual computational) negation of the Old MCR's Big-Bang Model of a "constantly" expanding universe: According to the Old MCR Paradigm's GRT "Big-Bang" Model, the universe's current rate of expansion can be explained based on three "Exceptional Expansive Events" (or factors, EEE's): 1) Initial "Big-Bang" Event: the creation of the entire physical universe based on an initial nuclear event. 2) Cosmological Factor: exceptional ("unexplained") anti-gravitational effect that is causing the universe's constant-rate increase in its expansion rate. 3) Purely hypothetical ("unexplained") "Dark-Matter" Concept: that is assumed (somehow) to "cause" an increase in the universe's expansion! However, even beyond the (perplexing) failure of Astronomers to experimentally detect the actual existence of this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept (for the past twenty years!?) even from a theoretical standpoint, this (purely hypothetical) Dark Matter (DM) concept – could not account for an increase in the universe's expansion rate! This is because even if there existed such a (purely hypothetical) DM concept (or element) – assumed to (somehow) "push" the outer-galactic elements in the universe, it could only do so at a "constant-rate", e.g., because it's quantity cannot increase over time! This means that over time, the rate of the universe's expansion could only remain constant – or (much more likely) decrease!

In fact, the very (computational) structure of GRT's (three) "Exceptional Expansive Effects" (EEE's), e.g., (1) "Big-Bang" (BB) event; (2) "Cosmological Factor" (CF); (3) "Dark-Matter" (DM) – all share two (very important) characteristics:

- a) These three EEE's are based on the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm's basic "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) structure; which has been shown by the G-D's Physics "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) to be "computationally flawed", i.e., lead to an inevitable "logical-inconsistency" and (ensuing) "computationally-indeterminacy", and are therefore negated by the CDP (as "invalid")!
- b) These three EEE's can only account for a "constant rate" of the universe's expansion (e.g., or more likely a "decreasing rate" of the universe's expansion) "over time" – but cannot account for an "increased rate" of the universe's expansion over time!?

Indeed, when we examine each of these three EEE's (e.g., individually), we can see that none of them can account for an "increasing rate" of the universe's expansion: a) The "Big-Bang" (initial) nuclear event cannot account for an increasing rate of the universe's expansion, since the initial "impetus" of the Big-Bang's nuclear explosion necessarily pushes the universe's outer galactic elements at a certain "constant" rate, (e.g., or more likely will decrease over time) but will not "increase" over time! b) The "Cosmological Constant" – despite it being "unexplainable": e.g., there is no "etiological" physical explanation for its repulsive effect, or the nature of such an effect; in any event such an "axiomatic repulsive effect" must also be "constant"! This is due to the fact that this "Cosmological Constant" has been defined as "constant"! c) "Dark-Matter" (DM): this purely hypothetical DM – despite the fact that it could not be detected experimentally (for the past twenty years, despite numerous attempts to do so!?) could only "push" those outer galactic regions in a "constant" (e.g., or more likely a "decreasing" rate) over time; this i.e., because, once again, unless this "DM" could somehow "increase in quantity" (over time), its effect could not "increase" over time!

Indeed, an examination of the SRCS Computational Structure of each of these three EEE's has revealed that they all share the same basic SRCS' (intrinsic) "computational flaw", which is exposed through the CDP – and points at the inevitable existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP), which according to the G-D'S PHYSICS (simultaneously) computes all exhaustive spatial points in the universe Paradigm at the "unfathomable" rate of $c2/h = 1.36-50$ (sec)!

The "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) Negation of the GRT's SRNCS Structure!

According to G-D's Physics' "Computational Duality Principle" Postulate, the basic "Computational Structure" of GRT's Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., termed: a "Self-Referential Negative Computational System" (SRNCS) is "computationally flawed", i.e., it inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" – which are contradicted by GRT's Computational System's proven empirical capacity to determine the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion, thereby pointing at the singular higher-ordered UCP that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe! Specifically, the GRT's SRNCS Computational Structure assumes that it is solely based on the direct physical interactions (di) between GRT's basic "Curved Space-Time" (due to the presence of certain "massive-objects") "Contractive-Stable Universe" [C-STMo : CSU], e.g., describing a universe that is fundamentally "contracting" or being "stable" (i.e., "constant"); and the three (abovementioned) EEE's "expulsive-effects", e.g.: BB, CF, and DM – all describing a (constant) "accelerated-expansion" of the universe produces such a SRNCS Computational Structure:

GRT's SRNCS:

PR[[C-STMo : CSU], [EEE-BB, CF,DM]] → "Not C-STMo : CSU" / di ?!
Wherein it is assumed that GRT's fundamentally assumed "Contractive-Stable Universe" (e.g., due to the curvature of Space-Time by certain "massive objects") : [C-STMo : CSU] seems to both "exist" and "Not exist" at the same "di" computational level, e.g., constituting a basic "logical-inconsistency" and associated "computational indeterminacy" implying an (apparent) inability of such a SRNCS System to determine the "existence" or "non-existence" of this [C-STMo : CSU]! But, since empirically the universe is in fact expanding (at an accelerated rate!), e.g., "Not [C-STMo : CSU]"; therefore, according to the CDP there must exist a singular higher-ordered UCP that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each UF's at the rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ")!

Announcement of G-D's Physics Call for Astronomers to Validate the UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction Through Precise & Longitudinal Measurements!

"G-D's Physics" Discovery of the "UNCIARE-JRH's MAI's-Accelerated Time Values" Critical Prediction!

So, we see that the universe's True Age stems from "G-D's Physics" discovery and empirical validation of the UNCIARE-JRH's MAI's increase in the rate of the universe's expansion (due to the CHCF occurring during the JRH's two days' time interval)! Surprisingly, we find that "G-D's Physics" (empirically validated) "UNCIARE-JRH" Critical Prediction also points at an additional "UNCIARE-JRH's Accelerated Time Value/s" (novel) "Critical Prediction!"

This is because, when we take into consideration the UCP's (novel) "Computational Definitions": of "Energy" and "Time", we begin realizing that the (abovementioned Results') empirical validation of the UNCIARE-JRH implies that since there is an annual (MAI) increase in the rate of the universe's expansion (beginning during the JRH's two days' of CHCF and continuing throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year); this implies that based on the UCP's (novel) Computational Definition of "Energy" as the degree of "Object-inconsistency" for any given object, such an empirically validated increased UNCIARE-JRH translates to a greater "Frame-inconsistency" "displacement" of any of the universe's objects!

"Energy"

E: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$
such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i\dots n)]$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

But, when we look at this UCP's Computational Definition of "Energy", we may notice that the UCP's computation of the degree of displacement of any such universal-object – is constrained and limited by Plack's constant as the maximal (possible) "displacement" of any such object across any two (subsequent) UF's frames! This means that if (nevertheless) the UCP is known to increase the abovementioned UNCIARE-JRH degree of displacement of all universal-objects – with every subsequent Jewish Year; then, the only manner in which such an UNCIARE-JRH increase in the objects-displacement could be achieved – is through an increase of the UCP's number of UF's frames comprising each subsequent Jewish Rosh Hashanah! But, once again, when we take a close look at the UCP's (novel) Computational Definition of "Time", we can notice that the "time-value" of any given event or phenomenon is given based on the number of object-inconsistency presentations across a given series of UF's frames! However, if the number of UF's frames comprising every subsequent Jewish Year increases according to UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction, - then this also points at a novel (and surprising) "UNCIARE-JRH's Accelerated Time Values" "Critical Prediction, i.e., wherein the actual rate of universe's time is accelerated by the UCP for each subsequent Jewish Year!"

This is based on the UCP's (novel, abovementioned) Computational Definition of "Energy" – which is constrained by a "maximal displacement" limit of "Planck's constant";

"Energy"

E: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$
such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i\dots n)]$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

This means, that "G-D's Physics" (empirically validated) UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction, e.g., indicating a greater rate of the universe's expansion (for each subsequent Jewish Year), i.e., indicating an increased "Energy" level for every universal-object's (movement) – must necessarily point at an increase in the actual number of Universal Frames (UF's) series comprising the new Jewish Year! Hence, according to this (novel) "UNCIARE-JRH's Universe's-Accelerated Time Values" "Critical Prediction", the number of UF's frames comprising that entire subsequent Jewish Year should be greater than the number of UF's frames comprising (any preceding) year!

But, since the UCP's (novel) Computational Definition of "Time" relates to the degree of "Object-inconsistent" computations:

"Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

T: $\sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}[UF(n)] \neq O_{i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}\{UF(i\dots n)\}] / c * n \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$
such that: $T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - [O_{j\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in

which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Then this implies that according to "G-D's Physics" empirically validated **UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction** there should also exist "G-D's Physics" **"UNCIARE-JRH's Universe's Accelerated Time Values"!** In other words, the "Time-Values" of any New Jewish Year is accelerated (e.g., contains a greater number of time-points) than the preceding Jewish Year!

In other words, "G-D's Physics" empirically validated UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's rate of expansion stems – not from the purely hypothetical (and in fact "superfluous", i.e., "non-existent", purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept, but instead from the UCP's increase in the UCP's number of UF's comprising any subsequent Jewish Year, indicating the "UNCIARE-JRH's Universe's Accelerated Time Values"!

Indeed, in order to test for this (potentially far reaching) new "UNCIARE-JRH's Universe's Accelerated Time Values" Critical Prediction, a call for validation of two additional (unique) "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" New (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm is herein made:

"G-D's Physics Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" Based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" (unique) "Critical Prediction" regarding the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated findings, indicating that the UCP's differential computation of the "Mass" value/s of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle than the (equivalent negatively charged) electron particle – led to the Muon's associated "altered Muon Hydrogen Proton's" measurements as more "spatially-consistent" (e.g., according to "G-D's Physics" new UCP's Computational Definitions of "Mass") than the equivalent "Standard Hydrogen Proton" (see above Results); therefore an even more direct empirical measurement of "G-D's Physics" "Differential Mass UF's Appearances" Critical Prediction regards a comparison of an Accelerator's precise measurements of the significantly greater number of times that such a ("more massive") Muon particle would appear across a given series of UF's frames(i.e., or in fact a certain measurable sample thereof!) than the "less-massive" electron particle!

Therefore, it may be said that these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings lay the (theoretical) foundations for the prospective "G-D's Physics Differential-Mass UF's Appearances" Critical Prediction; because they indicate that the "more massive" Muon particle is measured as "spatially more consistent" than the (relatively) "less massive" particle, i.e., both in its "proton-radius size" and its "spatial measurement accuracy"! Indeed, the aim of this (prospective) **"G-D's Physics Differential-Mass UF's Appearances"** (unique) "Critical Prediction" is to test "G-D's Physics" (novel) conception of "Mass" as representing the UCP's computation of an "Object-consistent" measure":

"Mass"

M: $[O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - [O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i..n)] \leq n * h \{[UF's(i..n)]$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

Specifically, the aim is to test a direct (prospective) **"G-D's Physics Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances"** (unique) "Critical Prediction": predicting that the (relatively) "more-massive" Muon particle would appear across a greater number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) than the "less-massive" electron particle: Contrasting between the number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM, e.g., see

below their mathematical calculation) in which a 'more massive particle' (i.e., the Muon), would be detected relative to a "less-massive" particle (i.e., the electron); It is suggested that in order to test "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" (unique) it is necessary to contrast the number of FTM in which the 'more-massive' 'Muon' relative appears, relative to the number of FTM in which the 'less-massive' electron particle would be detected; However, a key point to be noted is that the "temporal resolution" of most Accelerators is far less "sensitive" than the hypothesized rate at which the Universal Computational Principle (UCP) computes the series of USCF's frames, i.e., " $c^2/h=1.45\cdot 42 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " – with certain Accelerators reaching almost the speed of light " $c = 3.33\cdot 6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " (e.g., regarded as the 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' accuracy level in this experiment), producing a magnitude difference of $x\cdot 36 \text{ sec}^{-1}$; Nevertheless, it is suggested that even if we opt to "sample" the FTM's at such a "decreased" temporal resolution (below) the speed of light " $c = 3.33\cdot 6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ", i.e., in effect sampling a significantly decreased temporal accuracy level [e.g., $x\cdot 36 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ decreased magnitude of accuracy relative to the rate at which the Universal Computational Principle (UCP) computes the series of USCF's frames (i.e., " $c^2/h=1.45\cdot 42 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ "); we can still expect that the "more massive" Muon particle would appear at a greater percentage of these " $c = 3.33\cdot 6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " FTM's samplings relative to the number of (the same decreased accuracy) FTM's samplings in which the electron would be detected!

As stated above, in calculating "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" (unique) "Critical Prediction", e.g., regarding the significantly smaller number of FTM's in which the 'electron' particle would be detected relative to the number of (such) FTM's in which the 'Muon' may be measured, we need to correct for the known subatomic (quantum theory related) bias towards a slightly "easier" measurement of such 'more-massive' 'Muon' particle relative to the measurements of a 'less massive' 'electron' particle; In other words "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" "Critical Prediction" regarding the significantly greater FTM's at which the 'more massive' Muon particle (M) would be detected, relative to the number of (equivalent) FTM's at which the 'less-massive' electron (e) particle would be detected should subtract the "quantum measurement bias" (QMB) towards a more 'sensitive temporal measurement' of more massive particle:

FTM(M) – QMB >FTM(e)

To the extent that this **"G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances"** "Critical Prediction" is empirically validated, then this would provide an unequivocal validation for "G-D's Physics" ACC New Paradigm – specifically, for its novel conception of the manner in which that singular higher-ordered UCP differentially computes relatively more massive than less massive particles; More generally, it will validate "G-D's Physics" (potentially far reaching) new understanding that according to the number of UCP's "Object-consistent" computations of any given (relativistic or quantum) "object" – its "Mass" value is given! Conversely, according to the differential "Object-inconsistent" UCP's computations, any given (relativistic or quantum) "object's" "Time" values is computed!

"G-D's Physics' Accelerated Temporal Measurements" Critical Prediction!

Another (even more direct)experimental validation of "G-D's Physics" novel **"G-D's Physics' Accelerated Temporal Measurements" Critical Prediction!** Involves the usage of the abovementioned **"G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances"** experimental setup – but geared towards the comparison of the number of FTM's presentations of the "more massive" Muon particle relative to the number of FTM's of the "less-massive" electron particle; Compared to these "Muon's" & electron's presentations – found within the New Jewish Year (relative to

the preceding Jewish Year), which is predicted to increase significantly! Specifically, it is predicted that the value of the increase in the number of FTM's of either the (more massive) Muon, or of the (less-massive) electron – in the New Jewish Year (relative to the preceding Jewish Year) would be derived from the abovementioned "G-D's Physics" stipulated MAI increase in the universe's measured expansion rate (for each subsequent Jewish Year)!

G-D's Physics' Novell Computational Definition of the "Gravitational Force" Metamorphosizes "Space-Time" Curvature!

G-D's Physics' Novell Computational Definition of the "Gravitational Force" Metamorphosizes "Space-Time" Curvature!

Instead, G-D's Physics' New ACC Scientific Paradigm explains GRT's "Gravitational Force" – not as "caused" by (certain) "massive objects" causing the "curvature of space-time" (i.e., which is negated by "G-D's Physics" new ACC Paradigm, as explained above); but rather through "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's computational definition of "Mass" (e.g., of any given subatomic particle or of any relativistic object) – as the degree of "Object-Consistent" presentations of any such "object" across a given series of UF's frames!

"Mass"

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - [O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

Surprisingly, this novel UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given (subatomic particle or relativistic) "object" offers an entirely new understanding of the "curvature of Space-Time", as well as of the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; which when taken together with the (simultaneous) UCP's computation of the other three Physical Features (for every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe!) allows "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm to completely unify (for the first time in Physics!) between those Four basic Physical Features, as well as between GRT & QM! Indeed, according to The New "G-D's Physics" UCF's simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic Physical Features creates (relatively) "consistent regions" (i.e., within a given "location" in the "coordinates" of the "Universal Frame" – across a series of UF's frames!): which may be characterized as "High-Mass; Low Energy" ("HMLE") "consistent regions, represented by the large "red" circles (in Figure 1); As opposed to other "Low-Mass; High-Energy" (LMHE) which appear as (relatively) "inconsistent-regions" (e.g., within a given "location" in the "coordinates" of the Universal Frame – across a series of UF's frames!); Hence, as we can see (in Figure 1) the UCP's computation of "differential consistency regions": a) The "HMLE" "consistent regions" of the "large Red circles", which remain "spatially-consistent" across the two UF's frames; as opposed to : b) The "LMHE" "inconsistent regions" of the "small (alternating) blue/white" which continuously "alternate" (i.e., are "spatially inconsistent") across the two illustrated UF's frames! This implies that those LMHE (alternating "blue/white circles") create a "vacuum" or an "empty-alternating space" around those "consistent" HMLE ("Red circle), thereby giving rise to the "appearance" of "curved Space-Time" around those HMLE "consistent Red circles"!

The UCP's "Gematria-Based" THCD's Computation!

Thus, we begin conceiving of an entirely new physical universe – which does not exist (any longer) as an "independent-objective" (continuous) physical reality, but rather only exists as a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of that singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality": which guides the entire physical universe towards that "Ultimate Per-

fectured Geulah Goal State" based on its THCD's Dimensions' computation; Indeed, "G-D's Physics" previous (in-depth) analysis of these THCD's UCP's computation revealed that there exist a few converging "computational layers" for this singular higher-ordered UCP's computation of the THCD's, e.g., that also involves the UCP's "Gematria" (i.e., Hebrew alphabet numeric values – corresponding to any given "object's" UCP's computation of the four basic Physical Features)!

Based on the discovery of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, and its shown capacity to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and more importantly, its empirical validation of two of its unique "Critical Predictions", as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM; we now reach another "pivotal point" along the development of this New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm of 21st century Theoretical Physics: Since the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm stipulated an "A-Causal Computation" stemming from the discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, which points at the impossibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, existing either in the same- or different UF's frame/s, then this points at the need for this singular higher-ordered UCP to compute all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising the entire physical universe) for each consecutive UF's frame/s! However, thus far, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm's discovered "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" (THCD-UCF) was only capable of explaining (in general terms) the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") based on its stipulated two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" (of "Consistency" and "Framework") combinations! In other words, those four basic physical features are computed by this singular UCP as "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or as "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computational measures of the degree of "consistency" or "inconsistency" of any given exhaustive spatial pixel's "object" across a series of UF's frames!

Moreover, the general (overall) conception of the origination- sustenance- and "Ultimate Goal" of the universe's development by this singular UCP has given us an overall (good) overall understanding of the general framework for "G-D's Physics" New scientific explanation of the universe's existence and development; What's still "missing" is a "minute-detailed" understanding of the manner in which this UCP "differentiates" between its computation of these four basic physical features for every individual "object", i.e., "inanimate" or "animate"! The suggested new "Gematria Consistency Computation" (GCC) "fills" this "gap" and offers a new conceptual explanation for the manner in which this UCP can compute those four basic physical features (e.g., as "differentiating" their values for any specific "inanimate" or "animate" object)! The basic assumption underlying this new "GCC" facet of "G-D's Physics" THCD-UCF is that based on the (Hebrew) Alphabet's "naming" of every such ("animate" or "inanimate") object, the UCP computes those four (integrated) basic physical features, e.g., through the usage of the five (subsequent) HCD (following the initial three "General Plan" of the UCP's origination and development of the physical universe, i.e., of "Wisdom"/"המכח", "Computation"/"הניב" & "Reversed Time Eulah Goal Consistency"/"תעד")!

These five subsequent HCD comprise of: "Chassed", "Gevorah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod", which are each stipulated to be comprised of the "ten total HCD's ten "zero's" minute temporal computation of the UCP – totaling the UCP's overall rate of computation for each exhaustive spatial pixel (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! In other words, the manner in which the UCP can compute each and every exhaustive spatial pixel object's four basic physical features is based on a combination of its unique "name" – according to its "Gematria" computation, based on those "subsequent five"

("Chessed", "Gevorah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod" HCD) detailing of each of the given "name's" (Hebrew) letters equivalent numeric value!

In other words, we obtain (e.g., for the first time in Theoretical Physics) a "Non-Material Gematria Consistency Computation" (NMGCC) of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe! This new "G-D's Physics" NMGCC conception of the manner in which the singular higher-ordered UCP is capable of computing each and every "object" in the physical universe – based on its "Gematria" (Hebrew Letters' numerical value) as representing the number of times that every exhaustive spatial pixel is presented across a certain series of UF's frames! Since we've already seen, that the UCP computes the "mass" value of any given object as its computation of the number of times this object has been presented (as "spatially-consistent") across a series of UF's frames! This means that the current discovery of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm's "NMGCC" capability of the UCP to "translate" the given "Gematria" numerical value of any given "objects" (Hebrew) name into the UCP's computation of the five "secondary-essential" Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD): "Chessed", "Gevorah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod", such that each of these HCD

possesses all ten HCD's corresponding to "ten zero's" out of the "fifty zero's" representing the rate of the UCP's overall rate of UF's computation, i.e., $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ (sec)! This means for instance, that the Hebrew letters for the word "human-being" "אדם" comprise these three letters "א", "ד", "מ" which correspond to the "Gematria" of "1-0000000000" [1-10], "4-0000000000" [11-20] & "40-0000000000" [21-30] denoting the cumulative number of times that a "human-being" is presented across a series of UF's frames – with a special significance for the corresponding unique Gematria numerical value for each of those (potential) five "secondary-essential" HCD ("Chessed", "Gevorah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod")! In other words, the specific (Hebrew) "Gematria" for a "human-being" comprises a very unique and specific composition of three (out of the five) "secondary-essential" HCD: "Chessed", "Gevorah" & "Tiferet", with each one of them possessing a specific numerical value which can be translated to the UCP's computation of a human-being's "mass", or in fact any other of the four (completely integrated) basic physical features (of "time", "space" or "energy"), based on the earlier mentioned "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD-UCF):

FIGURE: "GIMATRIA-CONSISTENCY COMPUTATION" (GCC) TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (GCC-THD-UCF):

FIGURE 4: The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

Noteworthy, is the fact that we can perhaps “infer” some of these four basic physical features based on the specific HCD’s comprising each “object” – such as for instance, in the case of the UCP’s computation of the four basic physical features of a “human-being” based on his Hebrew names specific “Gematria” (three initial) HCD’s numerical values, and understanding of the “corresponding” HCD’s key characteristics: for instance, the fact that “סגא” only possesses the three initial HCD’s of “Chessed”, “Gevurah” & “Tiferet” (but not the two subsequent “Netzach” & “Hod” HCD), indicating that the UCP’s computation of a “human-being” corresponding to the UCP characteristics of “Chessed”: its natural tendency to “give” or to “nurture” (and “grow”), “Gevurah”: the UCP’s tendency to “measure” and “limit” its “giving” and “nurture”; & “Tiferet”: The UCP’s capacity to “balance” and “integrate” between these apparently “opposing” (“Chessed” & “Gevurah”) UCD (with a leaning towards the “Chessed” HCD in this “Tiferet” HCD)! More specifically, these three “Gematria” Hebrew Letters’ specific numerical value also indicates the relative significance of each of these three (initial HCD: “Chessed”, “Gevurah” & “Tiferet”): Thus, for instance, the fact that amongst these three initial three HCD, it is primarily the “Tiferet” HCD which possesses the highest numerical value: “40-30” (sec!) implies the UCP’s computation of a “human-being” is based upon the unique capacity of human-beings to “integrate” between the first letter of “א” associated with “Chessed”: characterized by the Hebrew first letter “א” – which also represents “G-D” (since the Hebrew word for “G-D” is “מִיְקוּלָא” which begins with this same “א” (Alef) letter and which is characterized by: “Goodness”, “Giving”, “Spirituality” etc.; and the second letter of “ד” (which also stands for the Hebrew word for “blood” signifying the “human body” – such that this integration of the “physical bodily” element with the “Divine” (“Spiritual”) element is achieved and is also “leaning towards expressing” (more) the Divine element!

Interestingly, the Hebrew word for “Earth” or “soil” is very similar to Hebrew word for a “human-being” “המאד” which has the addition of a fourth letter “ה” associated with the fourth “Secondary-essential” (five) “HCD’s”: “Netzach” הצנ which signifies the UCP’s capacity to “overcome any obstacle/s” for the fulfillment of its ultimate “Geulah Goal” of obtaining a “Perfected”: “Moral” & “Spiritual” state of Humanity and the universe! This may imply that whereas a “human-being” is embedded with the characteristics of his ability to “integrate” and “uplift” his “bodily-material” nature with his “Divine” aspect, i.e., based on his given “Gevurah” and “Tiferet” HCD’s; in the case of the Hebrew word for “Earth”, the UCP adds the fourth HCD of “Netzach” which allows the “Earth” to serve as a “vehicle” to “manifest” and “overcome” any “obstacles” for the fulfillment of the UCP’s ultimate “Geulah Goal Perfected State” of Humanity and of the universe!

Another pertinent example of the significance of this (newly discovered) “G-D’s Physics” “Non-Material Gematria Consistency Computation” (NMGCC) may be the Hebrew word for “G-D”: “מִיְקוּלָא” which comprises all of those “five” “secondary-essential” HCD’s letters! Once again the first letter of the “Chessed” Dimension is “א” (Alef) which signifies not only the first letter of the Alphabet, but also represents “G-D”! The second letter is “ל” which represents the “Gevurah” HCD (“G-D’s” “fierce force” of “overcoming any obstacles”); “ה” 5” in “Gematria”) for the third letter corresponding to the third “Tiferet” HCD signifying the UCP’s capacity to “integrate” the five HCD’s (as well as signifying the “third initial HCD’s of “Binah” or “Computation, i.e., the UCP’s capacity to organize, plan and compute the entire “Blue-Print Plan” of the whole development of the universe from its “inanimate” (initial) manifestation through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards the “Ultimate Geulah Goal” Perfected state of the universe)! The fourth letter is “יוד” (“י”) standing for the “Netzach” HCD which is the UCP’s ability to “overcome” and “triumph” over any “obstacles” in order to advance the whole universe towards its Ultimate “Geulah Goal Perfected” State! This is significant, because the “Yud” letter also characterizes “G-D” (e.g., appearing as the first letter in

G-D’s holy name), and possesses the “Gematria” (10) representing the “Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions” (which points at the fact that the UCP’s capacity of “overcoming” and “obstacle/s” for the fulfillment of its Ultimate “Geulah-Goal Perfected State” of the universe stems from its THCD’s overall “Blueprint Plan” and its execution towards attaining this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal”! The final (sixth) letter is “ו” for the fifth HCD of “Hod” which signifies (according to “G-D’s Physics THCD”) the UCP’s enabling us as human-beings to do “Teshuva” (e.g., ask for “forgiveness” and “understanding” from “G-D”, preceded by our conscious decision to “change our behavior” (for the better), and try our best not to “repeat” any “moral misdeeds”; This fifth “Hod” HCD also encompasses the aspect of us as human-beings recognizing the “Beauty”, “Perfection” and “All-Goodness” of “G-D”!

So, we can see that the UCP’s computation of every (possible) “object” (i.e., “inanimate” or “animate”) is based upon its “Gematria” of the Hebrew letters: e.g., which possess both significance in terms of the five “secondary-essential” Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD’s) to which they belong (according to their order: the first letter belonging to the “Chessed”, second to “Gevurah” etc.) and their relative “Gematria strength”, e.g., both in terms of each Hebrew letter’s “numerical value” and their associated HCD’s value (i.e., “Chessed”: from -1-10; “Gevurah”: from -11 – 20; “Tiferet”: from -21—30; “Netzach”: -31 – 40; “Hod”: from -41 – 50 !). Hence, an emerging new facet of this new NMGCC discovery made by “G-D’s Physics” is the transformation of these Hebrew letters’ “Gematria”: e.g., “numerical value” of each letter, combined with its association with each of those respective five “secondary-essential” HCD’s – as determining the number of times that this object will be presented across a series of UF’s frames: which would determine its “mass” value(!) But, as we’ve seen, another (not less important) facet of this (newly discovered) NMGCC is the relative significance of each of the letters/specific HCD (based on its Gematria & HCD’s “zero’s strength”, as “glanced” from the above examples) pertaining to each object’s (Hebrew) letters.

One more significant discovery associated with this (novel) NMGCC perspective on how the UCP (continuously and simultaneously) computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe relates to those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s differentiation between “human-beings”, which possess a “free Moral Choice” and all other “inanimate and animate” forms which do not possess this “free Moral Choice”! This is due to the fact that the execution of those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s depends on the UCP’s “allowance” (and in fact “pre-planning”) for human-beings to make those (precise) “free Moral Choice/s” as a part of its (overall) “Ultimate Geulah Goal”, e.g., of “steering” Humanity (and the whole physical universe) towards that “Perfected Geulah State”, in which all human-beings (and Humanity, as a whole) will recognize the “Oneness” of this singular “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (or “Universal Consciousness Reality”), its innate characters of “Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”, and our “inseparability” from It (and from each other)! Indeed, when we (closely) examine those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s we can sense that they are all “centered” or “anchored” in the UCP’s “Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle” (DEMP), e.g., whose “sole-aim” is to “teach” us (human-beings) our “inseparability” from this singular (higher-ordered) UCP – through our “free Moral Choice”! Thus, the “first” amongst those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s is “Chessed’s” “Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle” (DEMP)! This DEMP states that whenever any Individual human-being chooses an “Immoral Choice”, e.g., towards another Individual human-being, which causes “pain” or “suffering” (“G-d forbid”), then this necessarily “triggers” the UCP’s selection of an “equivalent negative situation”, in which that Individual human-being that inflicted “pain/suffering” would have to “experience” the same “negative situation” – in order for us to realize that such “Immoral Choice/s” is not “right” and should be “avoided”! “Implicitly”, since we begin “realizing” the “connection” that exists between any (negative) “Immoral Choice”

that we may have made – and our own experiencing of such a “negative situation” (e.g., of “pain or suffering”, “G-d forbid”), then this raises our “understanding” and “awareness” that we cannot make any such “Immoral Choices” but rather must “correct” our own “free Moral Choice/s” to constitute “positive Moral Choice/s”! (Once again, this implicit “Moral understanding” or “Moral awareness” that our “Moral/Immoral Choices” determine the “Moral/Immoral” “positive” or “negative” situations that we would experience (ourselves) makes us realize that we are really “inseparable” from each other, as “integral parts of this singular higher-ordered UCP!) Following this “Chessed’s” (HCD) “Dynamic-Equilibrium is the next HCD: “Gevurah” which possesses a “Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir” of all “past”, “present” and “multiple possible future/s” – for each Individual human-being depending upon (his or her) Moral/Immoral Choices (at each point in time), which already manifests the UCP’s computation of the specific future for each individual human –being based on their specific Moral Choice/s; Next, follows the “Tiferet” HCD’s Collective Human Consciousness Focus Jewish “Rosh Hashanah” (CHCF-JRH) “Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe” (NCAEU), in which the UCP essentially computes the specific “future/s” UF’s for all Individual human-beings for the entire next year (and which also correlates to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus’ “triggering” a “Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe”); Then, follows the HCD’s of “Neztach’s” “UCP’s Computed Potential Object”, corresponding to actually computed (next) “future UF’s” value/s for each Individual human-being (based upon the previous HD’s computation of the DEMP’s precise selected future for each Individual human-being etc.); and finally, the “fifth” HCD of “Hod’s” “UCP’s Teshuva”, in which the UCP allows for a “Teshuva” of each Individual human-being (for any “Immoral Choices/s” they have made) which then would “prevent” the materialization of any potentially “negative state” (computed at the previous Neztach’s “UCP’s Computed Potential Object”)! So, we can see, that these “five-essential” HCD’s are (indeed) “centered” around the human capacity to select “Moral/Immoral Choices” based on the “free Moral Choice” (unique characteristic of human-beings (e.g., unlike any other “inanimate” or “animate”: “plants” or “animals”);

Once again, the UCP’s “motivation” underlying these “five-essential” HCD’s is closely related to the fulfillment of the UCP’s overall “Ultimate Geulah Goal” of steering the entire physical universe towards it “Perfected Geulah State” (e.g., “Morally”, “Spiritually” and even “Physically”)! Since the whole “aim” and “Goal” of the universe’s creation- sustenance- and evolution- by this singular higher-ordered UCP is to evolve the whole universe from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: animals, plants and human-beings to the Ultimate “Geulah Goal” of the whole of Humanity realizing the singularity of this “Universal Computational/Consciousness Reality”, including its unique characteristics of the Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle” (DEMP), “All-Goodness”, “Peace and Harmony”; therefore those “five-essential HCD’s assist is “steering” Humanity (as a whole – as well as each Individual human-being) towards the attainment of this “Perfected Geulah Goal” State, through our experiencing of the “equivalent positive/negative state/s” produced by our Moral (or “G-d forbid”) Immoral Choice/s, and our ability to make “Teshuva” or to “learn” from those “negative” (“Immoral Choice/s” ensued) or “positive” (“Moral Choice/s produced) Choices! Interestingly, this new NMGCC discovery of “G-D’s Physics” new manner in which the UCP’s actually computes each and every object’s “Gematria-based” (Hebrew letters’ numerical value – as associated with these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s) is found to differentiate between the manner in which the UCP utilizes these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s – for human-beings (e.g., possessing a “free Moral Choice”) as opposed to the other “Non-Human”, e.g., “inanimate” and “animate”: plants and animals: As noted above, for human beings, the UCP’s utilization of these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s is aimed at “teaching” and “perfecting” our Moral nature such that we realize through these five “secondary-essential” HCD’s our “inseparability” from each other as well

as from this singular higher-ordered “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR), which is a part of the overall UCP’s advancement of Humanity (and the universe) towards the fulfillment of its “Ultimate Geulah Perfected Moral & Spiritual State”! Hence, in order to “teach” and “perfect” each and every Individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) through the operation of these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s the UCP utilizes each one of these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s based on each of these five HCD’s “ten zero’s” – as corresponding to the Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD’s)! This implies that in addition to the “basic” Gematria Consistency Computation (GCC) pertaining to each one of the letters comprising each Individual human-being’s “name” (and the more general GCC of the “general name” of a “human-being”, as discussed above), for each Individual human-being, based on (his or her) “Moral/Immoral Choice/s” (as discussed above) the UCP computes for each one of the 10 zero’s corresponding to each of those five “secondary-essential” the THCD’s complete “Moral rectification”! In contrast, for all “Non-Human” (NH) forms of “inanimate” matter or “animate”: plants and animals, the UCP computes only the GCC based computation of these five “secondary-essential” (as discussed above) based only on the Gematria (Hebrew letters numerical values associated with each one of these five “secondary-essential” ten zero’s values), i.e., without connection to the THCD’s overall Moral rectification)! One “exception” to this “neutrality” of the THCD’s association with the “ten zero’s” for “Non-Human” (NH) forms (of “inanimate” matter, “animate”: plants and animals) is all instances in which these NH objects are associated (in some form or fashion) to a Moral/Immoral Choice/s that a given Individual human-being has made, in which case it is possible that that NH “object” will be “included” or “affected” by that Individual human-being’s Moral/Immoral Choice/s (e.g., as manifesting through the human DEMP’s associated five “secondary-essential” HCD’s “ten-zero’s”)!

Thus, we see that the manner in which the UCP computes (simultaneously) all exhaustive spatial pixels (and “objects”) in the universe based on a “Non-Material Gematria Consistency Computation” is “non-material” (in nature)! As we’ve seen previously, due to the “A-Causal Computation” characterization of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm (e.g., stemming from the fact that there cannot exist any direct or indirect “material-causal” physical relationship/s between any two or more exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF’s frames due to the UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for every consecutive UF’s frame/s and the complete “dissolution” of the whole universe “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s); we’ve realized that since there cannot exist any such (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical relationship/s between any two (or more exhaustive) spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF’s frames, therefore there cannot be any “transference” or “effects” across any two consecutive UF’s frames: in other words, one UF’s cannot “affect” or “create” any “effect” or “influence” upon its subsequent UF’s frame/s! Instead, we have to look at the singular higher-ordered UCP – not only as the sole and singular “Universal Consciousness Reality” existing both “during” each of its consecutively produced UF’s frame/s, and also solely existing “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s, as the “Computational Invariance Principle” (of “G-D’s Physics New Scientific Paradigm) teaches us; But even beyond that, we realize (in this article) that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle (or Universal Consciousness Reality) computes each and every exhaustive spatial pixel’s object in the universe depends entirely upon this singular UCP’s Gematria based (Hebrew letters) Consistency Computation, which is “guided” based on the UCP’s or “Universal Consciousness Reality’s (UCR) overall “pre-planned” Blueprint for progressing the entire physical universe from inanimate “matter” through “animate”: plants, animals and human-being towards the “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” in which Humanity and Science will recognize the “Oneness”, “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” of this singular higher ordered

We've discovered in this (unique) article that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCR continuously creates- "dissolved"- re-computes- and evolves- every exhaustive spatial-pixel and object in the universe based on this NMGCC computation which differentiates between Human (H) and Non-Human (NH: "inanimate" matter, or "animate": plants and animals) by incorporating (in addition to the basic Gematria based computation of every object's Hebrew name as associated with those five "secondary-essential" HCD's ten zero's numerical value etc.) also the DEMP's manifestation through those five "secondary-essential" HCD's THCD's Moral rectification associated with the "ten-respective zero's"! We thus obtain an entirely new conception of the true nature of the physical universe – which is essentially "non-material": it is only a manifestation of the singular higher-ordered UCR (which constitutes the only "constant", "uniform" and "continuous" reality existing both "during" its production of each consecutive UF's frames comprising all exhaustive spatial pixels of the universe, as well as existing solely without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames), which has "pre-planned" the whole origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate "Perfected Geulah Goal" in which Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" characterized by "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! A Three-Phased UCP's Computation of the Human-Beings & the Universe! Indeed, a new (and fascinating) discovery made by the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (mostly in this profound article) is the fact that this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR requires three separate (yet somewhat "cumulative") phases for its computation and evolution of each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe: a) Gematria-Based Two "Object" Related Physical Features! According to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the UCP's (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising the entire physical universe!) is based on the Hebrew alphabetic numeric value, termed: "Gimatria": which is postulated to correspond to the "first" 25 "zero's", e.g., out of the 50 "zero's" ($c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$!) corresponding to the first five "HCD's" – each comprising five zero's! Intriguingly, these initial "25 zero's" produce the two (initial) "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") and "inconsistent" ("time") physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"! b) UCP's Six HCD's Dynamic-Equilibrium Geulah Driven Computation of Four Basic Physical Features c) The second phase of the UCP's computation of all Four basic Physical Features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" stems from the UCP's usage of the six (secondary) HCD's: Chessed, Gevurah, Tiferet, Nezach, Hod, Yesod, "I" which are each comprised of four "zero's" (out of the "fifty zero's" of the rate at which the UCP computes the series of UF's frame/s, e.g., $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$!) Since, as we've seen the previous (a) "Gematria UCP Computation" has already computed the two "Object-related" physical features of "Object-consistent" ("mass"), and "Object-inconsistent" ("time") (for all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe), therefore this second phase of the Six "HCD's Dynamic-Equilibrium Geulah Driven Computation of Four Basic Physical Features" progressively compute the four physical features – including also the two "Frame-consistent" ("space") and "Frame-inconsistent" ("energy") physical features, based on the "progressive accumulation" of these six secondary HCD's which are based on the "execution" and "materialization" of the UCP's "overarching" ("Consistency"-based) "Guiding Principles" of the "Dynamic Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP) and primary "Geulah-Driven Development of the Universe" (GDDU)! Indeed, as outlined above (and previously), the operation of these six secondary HCD's is geared towards restoring "moral-balance" and "steering" Humanity and the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"! Each of these six (secondary) HCD's dimensions "occupies" "4 zero's" so that collectively they account for "24 zero's" out of the total "50 zero's" (per second) in which this singular higher-ordered UCP computes

the entire physical universe each second! This means that the physical universe that we perceive of is not a "solid reality" but is actually being continuously "created" (computed), "dissolved", "re-created" (re-computed) and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second – i.e., through the UCP's continuous "cumulative computation" of the initial "Gematria-Based Consistency Computation" of the first five HCD's "Object-related" two physical features of "mass" and "time" (for all exhaustive spatial pixels/objects in the universe); followed by the Six HCD's Dynamic-Equilibrium Geulah Driven Computation of Four Basic Physical Features computation of the Four Physical Features; leading up to the actual "materialization" of all of exhaustive spatial pixels (and the whole physical universe) based on the third phase of "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions – Universal Computational Formula": d) "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions – Universal Computational Formula" ("Malchut") "I": In the third (completed) phase of the UCP's "progressively computed" universe (and all of its comprising exhaustive spatial pixels) which corresponds to the fiftieth "zero" the Infinite Intelligence (and Power) of this singular "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" integrates and produces between all of the hitherto computed Four basic Physical Features of the every exhaustive spatial pixel (Object) in the universe to produce an actually computed (completed) Universal Frame! In other words, we begin realizing that the entire physical universe (e.g., and all of its constituent exhaustive spatial pixels) is being produced continuously (and cumulatively) through the UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions based on the UCP's incessant "steering" of the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State – so many "trillions" of times each second! And that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP or UCR progressively constructs each consecutive UF's frame/s, for each consecutive UF's frame/s – as being cumulatively "added to" (by the UCP) through these "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's) based on the "three phases" described above! Therefore, we begin looking at the entire physical universe through a new "set of binoculars"; those of the UCP's/UCR's view of steering the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": "plants", "animals", "human-beings" – and up to the Ultimate Perfected Geulah State!

We begin comprehending that not only our Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's conception of the origination- and constitution- of the entire physical universe assumed to be "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" (random) nuclear event (e.g., which "created" all of the suns, galaxies, planets, energy, mass etc.); and the evolution of the universe – assumed to be mediated: a) on the "Biological facet, through Darwin's "Material-Causal" "Natural-Selection Principle"; and b) on the "Physical" facet – based on General Relativity Theory's (GRT) Einstein's Equations' conception of the accelerated expansion of the universe as being "caused" by the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts (which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which yet could not be detected experimentally despite over two full decades of trying to do so!)) Additionally, on the Physical level, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT (& QM) also assumes that the accelerated expansion of the universe is associated with the "Second Law of Thermodynamics" that postulates that the entire physical universe (e.g., as any Physical System) inevitably leads to an ever increasing level of Entropy which implies that all of the Suns will be extinguished, the universe expanding ("ad-infinity") and all of Life (on Earth) will be extinguished and dissipated! In stark contrast, the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) portrays an entirely different "picture" of the "origination"- and continuous "dissolution"- "re-computation" and "development" of the physical universe, based on a "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or "Universal Consciousness Reality", UCR) of developing the universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of the universe, e.g., in which Humanity (and Science) will

recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR, alongside its profound (and “sublime”) special characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” (according to which Humanity will live harmoniously)!

As we’ve already seen, based on the empirical validation of two (unique) “Critical Predictions” of the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm, e.g., as some valid than the New corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT and QM; The New “G-D’s Physics strictly negates the possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing either in the “same” or “different” UF’s frame/s) – and therefore also completely negates the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT’s assumption as if the universe was created by an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event (as mentioned above), nor can it expand (at an accelerated rate) due to the completely hypothetical “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” concepts (e.g., because as explained above there cannot exist any direct or indirect “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any such purely hypothetical “dark-matter”/“dark-energy” concept/s and any “galactic elements” that are assumed to be “pushed” by them?)! Indeed, the new (and profound) discovery (and understanding) brought about in this scientific article is that the continuous manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR “creates”- “dissolves”- “re-creates” and “evolves” every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the whole universe) is such that it progressively evolves and cumulatively computes every exhaustive spatial pixel, i.e., and every “object”: “inanimate matter”, “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards that “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State” of the universe! We realize that the UCP possesses an “Infinite Intelligence” – required to “progressively” and “cumulatively” compute the “Gematria-based” two “Object-related” physical features of “mass” and “time” (in the first 25 zero’s, out of the 50 zero’s describing the rate at which the UCP computes each consecutive UF’s frame/s! which translated into those two “Object-related” physical features of “mass” and “time”; then, the UCP utilizes the secondary six HCD’s Dimensions which take each of the resulting (exhaustive) “objects” (in the universe) which already possesses the two “Object-related” physical features of “mass” and “time” – in order to compute for it its two other “Frame-related” physical features of “space” and “energy”, resulting in each Object’s Four basic Physical Features Potential Object values (at the sixth secondary “Yessod” HCD): this secondary phase possesses an additional 24 zero’s connected with the computation of those Four basic Physical Features (e.g., $6 \times 4 = 24$) progressively and cumulatively computed at each of these six (secondary) HCD’s! The intriguing (and surprising) aspect of this new discovery of “G-D’s Physics” (current article) is that the UCP’s computation of these six (secondary) HCD’s is closely related to- (and in fact determined by-) the UCP’s “Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle” (DEMP) and the “Geulah Driven Development of the Universe” (GDDU)! In other words, we see that a key element that “drives” the universe towards its “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State”, and specifically the ongoing UCP’s computation of the Four Physical features which is shown to comprise of the UCP’s six-secondary HCD’s “centered” around the DEMP’s “moral/immoral choice/s” that each individual human-being makes and the UCP’s execution of a “parallel moral/immoral situation” in which this human-being is allowed to experience the same “positive” or “negative” (e.g., one of “multiple possible future/s”) UF’s frame’s situation! In other words, the “driving force” behind the UCP’s ongoing continuous (and “cumulative”) computation of each subsequent UF’s frame/s is the UCP’s DEMP’s computation of the “corrective”/“remuneration” for each “moral”/“immoral-choice/s” of each individual human-being (at any point in time), and the UCP’s “driving” of Humanity and the whole universe towards its “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State”! This surprising new discovery of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm points at both the centrality of our own human free-moral choice/s, and their “correction” or “reinforcement” by this singular (higher-ordered) UCP’s DEMP’s selection of one of multiple possible future’s which determines the Four basic Physical Features – in an ongoing “pro-

gressively cumulative” UCP’s computation comprising each consecutive UF’s frame/s (24 zero’s – out of 50 zero’s for those six secondary HCD’s)! Hence, the new understanding of “G-D’s Physics” (current) scientific understanding is that the physical universe was not created (or “caused”) by an initial nuclear “Big-Bang” event; that its accelerated rate of expansion is not due to any (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” or “dark-energy”; Nor, that the basic dynamics of the development of the universe is “caused” by any direct “material-causal” physical interaction/s between certain “massive objects” and their assumed “curving of Space-Time” (or conversely, that the “travelling pathways” of these “massive” and other “less-massive” objects is “caused” by this assumed curvature of Space-Time); Likewise, “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm negates Darwin’s “Natural Selection Principle” (as shown previously) once again due to “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” negation of the possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any given organism and the assumed “cosmic-rays” “causing” of any (“random genetic mutations”), nor between any given organism and its (“challenging”) exhaustive Environmental Factors (e.g., due to the simultaneity of the UCP’s computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for any consecutive UF’s frame/s, and the complete “dissolution” of the entire physical universe back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frames!)) Rather, the universe is seen as comprising only one singular reality, e.g., of the “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) that exists both “during” its continuous computation of every consecutive UF’s frame/s (simultaneously for all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features – which were discovered to be computed in three-phases, as described above), and also solely exists “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s; wherein the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels/objects (including: “inanimate” matter, and “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings) are seen as only “transient-phenomenal” manifestations of this singular UCR! Moreover, according to this New “G-D’s Physics” (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm this singular higher-ordered UCR is incessantly “steering” the entire physical universe – from its initial “inanimate” matter, through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards the “Ultimate Geulah Goal State” of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCR and recognize its “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” and hence lead a “Moral”, “Peaceful” and “Harmonious” life... Indeed, we come to realize that this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal” State of the physical universe – is obtained with the empirical validation of two of “G-D’s Physics” unique “Critical Predictions” as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM, thereby accepting “G-D’s Physics” recognition and acceptance of this new (profound) “Geulah Perfected State”!

"G-D's Physics" "Universal Consciousness Reality's" (UCR's) Geulah-Driven Universe!

So, we’re reaching an altogether new conception of the whole origination- sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe: not as originated by any (initial completely hypothetical) “Big-Bang” nuclear event, nor as being sustained and developed based on direct (or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions – either between (certain) Relativistic “massive objects” and their “curvature of Space-Time” (or conversely that such assumed “curved Space-Time” “causes” or “determines” the travelling-pathways of these “massive” and other “less-massive” objects), or between certain subatomic “probe” and “target’s (assumed) probability wave-function” elements which “causes” the “collapse” of this “target’s probability wave-function” into a singular complimentary space-energy / mass-time value! This Old “Material-Causal-Random” (MCR) Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) has also been directly negated through “G-D’s Physics” (novel) “Computational Duality Principle” (CDP, as shown above and previously) indicating that the MCR’s basic SCRC Computational System inevitably leads to both “logical inconsistency” and ensuing “computational indeterminacy” that are contradicted by these

Relativistic or Quantum (apparently) SRCS Systems capacity to determine their resulting empirical outcome; which inevitably leads to the CDP's discovered (singular higher-level) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50} \text{ sec}!$ thereby producing an extremely rapid series of UF's frames (comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point")!

Indeed, the negation of the Old MCR's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model – as less accurate than "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm has been evinced based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" (unique) UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction", indicating an increase in the universe's expansion rate, e.g., from its early Cosmological value to its current Astronomical (increased) rate, thereby resolving the Old MCR's GRT's "Big-Bang" "unexplained" "Hubble's Tension" Enigma. (As explained above, according to that Old MCR's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model, the three "Exceptional Expulsive Effects" [EEE's] may only account for a "constant-rate expansion" of the universe – but fail to explain the empirically observed "Hubble's Tension", which was in fact explained and predicted by "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction"!?) Thus, we find that the centrality of the JRH's two days "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) as brining about the UNCIARE-JRH's UCP's increase in the universe's expansion rate – also points at a (novel) "Universe's True Age" of 5785 years (as indicated above)!

Based on this unequivocal empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century Physics Scientific Paradigm, it has been shown to not only be capable of completely unifying between GRT & QM based on its discovery of the UCP's (novel) "Universal Computational Formula" – but also unify between the Four basic Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "space" and "time", for the first time in Physics!) as well as between the Four Forces, thereby going beyond the Standard Model (i.e., unifying between GRT's "Gravitational Force" and the other Three Forces as embedded within this singular UCF)! Indeed, a key (major) accomplishment of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (for Twenty-First Century Physics) is its alternative (new) explanation for the Gravitational Force, e.g., the apparent "curvature of Space-Time" (shown above) which stems from "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm which (strictly) negates the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in either the "same" or "different" UF's frames!?) Hence, as shown above this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm reexplains the apparent "curvature of Space-Time" as being produced through the UCP's differential computation of regions of "High-Mass, Low Energy" vs. other regions of "Low-Mass, High-Energy" which gives us the impression of a "curved Space-Time", but which (in truth) stems only from this UCP's differential computation of such HMLE vs. LMHE regions!?

Indeed, once we begin "transcending" the Old MCR's basic assumption wherein it is the direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature of Space-Time" etc. or between a certain subatomic "probe" and corresponding "target's (assumed) probability wave-function"; based on "G-D's Physics" discovered "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm (e.g., which negates any such direct or even indirect "material-causal" physical interac-

tion/s between any two or more exhaustive spatial pixel/s due to the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single or multiple UF's frame/s "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s back into the singularity of the UCP!) we are "forced" to begin viewing the whole existence- sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe – solely from the perspective of this singular higher-ordered "A-Causal Computation" UCP's (or UCR's) computational perspective! Hence, as shown above, "G-D's Physics" profound new two Theoretical Postulates – i.e., of the "Computational Invariance Principle" and (closely associated) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) clearly alter our whole fundamental understanding of the true nature- origination- dynamics- and development- of the entire physical universe: not as existing as an "independent-objective-continuous" physical reality, but rather as existing only as a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" which solely exist both "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (which this singular UCP "simultaneously" computes all of its exhaustive spatial pixels' Four Physical Features), as well as "solely exists" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe – which "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP!)

Indeed, this profound new realization brought about by "G-D's Physics" discovery of the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) as the sole "computationally invariant" reality that exists "constantly", "continuously" and "uniformly" – both "during" each consecutive UF's that it computes ("simultaneously", e.g., at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50} \text{ sec}!$), and also solely exists "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe!); has led to "G-D's Physics" in-depth analysis (and investigation) of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP's/UCR's THCD's and "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal", which "guide" and "direct" this singular UCP's/UCR's "steering" of the universe towards the fulfillment and realization of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the whole Universe! In this manner, this profound (breakthrough) article delineates the complete manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCR has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe – from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State, in which Science and Humanity (at large) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR, which is also characterized by such "sublime" characteristics as "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony", e.g., which will also characterize Humanity's existence and behavior at this "Perfected Geulah Goal" State! We realize that the universe must have been created in Six Days (see above and previously) because of the necessity for the (abovementioned) essential "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) to exist (from the sixth day onwards) in order for the empirically observed UNCIARE-JRH to exist! We therefore know that based on this (empirically validated) "UNCIARE-JRH" Critical Prediction (and further prospective empirical validations of additional "Longitudinal & Precision UNCIARE-JRH" Critical Predictions and Call for Astronomers', above) that the True Age of the universe is not 13.8B Years as hypothesized by the Old MCR's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model, but rather "G-D's Physics" newly discovered UNCIARE-JRH's asserted 5785 years (associated with this CHCF's AMI's, which are called for further direct empirical validation by Astronomers!)

Figure 5: "G-D's Physics" Alternative Explanation for "Curved Space-Time"!

UF 1

UF 2

Another part of the great "elegance" of this New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (e.g., empirically proven to be more valid e.g., in two of its unique "Critical-Predictions" than the corresponding predictions of the Old "MCR": GRT & QM Paradigm); is that its novel computational definition of the UCP's computation of the "mass" value of any given (relativistic or quantum) "object" allows it to derive an altogether new alternative explanation for the apparent "curvature of Space-Time" by (certain) "massive" objects! Since (as mentioned above and previously), according to the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single (or even multiple) UF's (e.g., due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!); therefore this New ACC "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is shown capable of deriving an "appearance" of those "HMLE" (e.g., "large Red circle") "consistent regions" remaining relatively "stable" across a series of UF's frame/s, as opposed to the "inconsistent regions" of those "LMHE" (e.g., alternating "blue/white small circles") which produces a "vacuum" or "empty-space" around those "HMLE -consistent regions", thereby giving rise to the appearance of a "curved Space-Time" around those "HMLE" ("Red circle")!

In other words, we see that the current (breakthrough) article's discovery of "G-D's Physics" "UNCIARE-JRH's Accelerated Time Values" completely unifies between the "macroscopic-relativistic" scale and the "microscopic-quantum" scale – in an entirely new theoretical understanding, wherein it is that singular higher-ordered UCP's annual increase in the number of UF's comprising any New Jewish Year, associated with "G-D's Physics" empirically validated UNCIARE-JRH which is also responsible for the (otherwise "unexplained") "Hubble's Tension"! Indeed, as shown above (and previously), "G-D's Physics" complete unifies between GRT & QM, as well as between the Four basic Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") – also offers an alternative (novel) explanation for Relativity's "Space-Time curvature" stems not from a "material-causal" (direct) physical interaction between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of (adjacent) "Space-Time", but rather from the differential UCP's computation of relatively "High-Mass, Low-Energy" (HMLE) regions in comparison to other "Low-Mass, High-Energy" (LMHE) regions, which gives the appearance of such "curved Space-Time" (see Figure 1).

"G-D's Physics" New "Order of Time"

Thus, we can now approach "G-D's Physics" New "Order of Time" con-

ception, based on the whole delineation of "G-D's Physics" new "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, and the UCP's (abovementioned) "Gimatria's" fifty Zero's intricate computation of each subsequent UF's frame/s exhaustive spatial pixels – e.g., and comprising Objects' Gimatria's and Dynamic-Equilibrium Principle's ensued "UCP's Actual Computed Object" [26-24 "Zero's"] computing that particular Object's "mass", "time", "space" and "energy" Physical Features! This is because unlike the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm's conception of "time" as derived from the direct "material-causal" physical interaction/s – either between the relativistic observer and any given relativistic "phenomenon" (e.g., "object" or "event", as outlined earlier), or between a quantum-subatomic "probe" and (assumed) "target's probability wave-function" (e.g., which is assumed to "collapse" that "target's probability wave-function"); "G-D's Physics" new "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm's conception of "time" negates the very possibility of the existence of any such direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., existing either in the "same" of "different" UF's frame/s as indicated above) due to the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s! Instead, "G-D's Physics" new "Order of Time" realizes that the UCP's computation of the "time" value of any given "object" in the universe comprises an intricate series of "inter-dependent" computations, including (i.e., listed in the "reverse-order" from the "end-result" actual computation of any given "object's" actual "time-value" through its "preceding" UCP's computations/order): a) the UCP's "Object-inconsistent" ("time") computation of the "UCP's Actual Computed Object" representing the "end-result" actual computation of any given "object's" "time-value" (or any other three Physical Features' actual computed value/s); b) the possibility of the UCP's computation of a possible "Teshuvah" for any individual human-being – i.e., regarding any "immoral-action/s" that this particular individual may have acted, which without that "teshuvah" [sincere "remorse" over a specific "wrong" immoral action", and accompanying resolute decision not to repeat that "immoral action"] could "avert" and "replace" the UCP's Dynamic-Equilibrium's Principle's ensued "corrective-UF's" (frame/s) "equivalent situation" in which that particular individual would have to experience the same "immoral-action consequence" situation that he/she "inflicted pain/suffering" upon another individual human-being! c) Prior to that, there is the UCP's **Computed Potential Object** (חשבון) representing the preceding: d) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" [CHCF] "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" [UNCIARE] at the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" [JRH] (UCP's CHCF-UNCIARE-JRH, "תראפת" HCD,

representing the UCP's computation of the entire (new subsequent) Jewish New Year's exhaustive spatial pixels'/object's value/s! Significantly, the abovementioned "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "UCP's acceleration of the Time-Values" for each subsequent New Jewish Year- implies that all of those CHCF-UNCIARE-JRH "time-values" will be accelerated, i.e., comprise more "time-points" than of the preceding JRH's Years! [Please see also the attached Announcement of the "International Contest for Validation of "G-D's Physics" Critical Predictions", which also includes this unique Critical Prediction!] Thus, we can see that "G-D's Physics" discovered new UCP's "computational definition of time":

"Time"

The UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] \neq O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\} \text{ such that: } T: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

This (novel) UCP's Computational definition of "Time" also comprises an integral part of the UCP's UCF:

Figure 1: The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ \hline h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...n} [PxI (a...z)]

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy",

"mass" and "time".

Wherein the UCP represented by the Hebrew Letter "י" computes at an extremely rapid rate, e.g., of "c2/h" = 1.36-50 (sec') simultaneously every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising every consecutive UF's – including the UCP's complete integration of those Four basic Physical Features through the UCF's: s * e / t * m computation (e.g., for each exhaustive spatial pixel – from "a to z")!

This UCP's UCF also includes it's ("unfathomably") rapid computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s : c2/h" = 1.36-50 sec'! (e.g., and every comprising object's "time-value/s" computation!) points at the UCP's above-mentioned four (d) steps for computation of the "Time-Order" of every exhaustive spatial pixel's object/s in the universe!

Finally, we should not forget that according to "G-D's Physics" New (empirically proven) New Twenty-First Century Physics' Paradigm the whole "temporal development" of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular (higher-ordered) UCP/UCR based on its "Reversed-Time Geulah Driven Universe", i.e., from "inanimate", through "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings – to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" (in which Humanity and Science recognizes the singularity of this UCP/UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. which will also characterize Humanity's behavior and existence!)

In fact, based on the direct empirical proof for this UNCIARE-JRH's annual MAI's increase in the UCP's computed rate of the universe's expansion (alongside all of the other abovementioned empirical validations of "G-D's Physics" unique "Critical Predictions"), it is safe to state that Science (and Humanity) are now "entering"- and "beginning"- this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State!

Figure 2: G-D's Phys.UNCIARE & Univ. Age!

Indeed, we see that "G-D's Physics'" new discovery- (and empirical validation) of its "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm points at an entirely new "origination- "dynamics" and "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" as the basis for the existence and development of the entire physical universe! Moreover, according to this New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm the whole origination- sustenance- dynamics- and development- of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP to develop from an initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards attaining a Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity in which Science (and the whole of Humanity) will recognize this singularity of the UCP, and its characterization by such "intrinsic-sublime" properties as: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will therefore also characterize the existence and behavior of the whole of Humanity! Therefore, the current (truly) "historic-pivotal turning point" associated with the direct empirical validation of the G-D'S PHYSICS as more valid than both GRT & QM (e.g., and in fact completely unifying between them, as well as for the first time in Physics between the Four basic Physical Features: of "time", "space", "energy" and "mass", as well as between the Four basic Forces!) is not "limited" only to the sphere of Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics, or even Science (more generally), but in fact represents a Major Turning Point (and even "Apex") in the whole development of Humanity and the entire physical universe, i.e., since it points at the "fulfillment" of the UCP's "pre-planned" "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the entire physical universe, in which the whole of Humanity (finally) recognizes) this singular higher-ordered UCP, and lives accordingly in complete Peace & Harmony!

Hence, it may be appropriate to end this (significant) article with Maimonides' ("prophetic") description of the state of Humanity during this (predicted) "Perfected Geulah State":

Intriguingly then, "G-D'S PHYSICS" points at Humanity's (current) entering of the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" is extremely reminiscent of the Isaiah's (well-known) Prophecy: And they shall beat their swords into plowshares, and their spears into pruning hooks; nation shall not lift up sword against nation, neither shall they learn war anymore... (Isaiah 2:4) And the Great Maimonides' prophecy regarding "That time (of Geulah) there will be no hunger or war, jealousy or competition... and the whole World's preoccupation will be only to know "G-D"! (Hilchut Melachim, 12:3-5).

Dedication

This article is dedicated to the Lubavitcher Rabbi and his preceding Rabbi Harayaz (Rabbi Yosef Yitzchak), and to the Rabbi HARASHAB for the fulfillment of their Vision of brining the world to its Geulah Perfected State (of Maimonides' and Isaiah's Prophecy)!

AN INTERNATIONAL CONTEST FOR VALIDATION OF G-D'S PHYSICS' NEW TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY'S SCIENTIFIC PARADIGM'S "CRITICAL PREDICTIONS"!

Background & Significance:

The Journal recognizes Dr. Bentovish's (Bentwich) "G-D'S Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century Physics' Scientific Paradigm, i.e., with over 120 published (peer-reviewed) scientific articles; Indeed, two (unique) G-D's Physics' "Critical Predictions" have (recently) been empirically validated

as more accurate than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, thereby "crowning" "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century! One of these (two) empirical validations of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm pertains to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" ("UNCIARE") during the (stipulated) "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah's" (JRH's two days) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) Critical Prediction points at the existence of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that (simultaneously) computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe at the incredible rate of " $c/2/h = 1.36-50 \text{ sec}(!)$ " thereby allowing this singular UCP to produce an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" of the entire whole universe! In addition, this validated UNCIARE Critical Prediction indicates the existence of a (novel) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) theoretical postulate, which stipulates that whenever there exist such CHCF (of Millions of individual human-beings) on this singular UCP, then this brings about an increase in the UCP's rate of the universe's expansion!

Given the acceptance of "A call is made to all leading Astronomers, Cosmologists and Universities to collaborate with Dr. Bentovish (e.g., directly through his personal email: drbentwich@gmail.com) in validating two additional (prospective unique) "Critical Predictions" comprising:

A. Precise Astronomical Measurement of the UNCIARE-JRH's Critical Prediction: of an increase in the current Astronomical Value of the Universe's Expansion Rate, i.e., by a "*Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ that occurred during the last JRH: on Oct. 3rd -4th, 2024 (e.g., relative to the measured rate of the universe's expansion prior to Oct. 3rd- 4th 2024; with this increased MAI value carrying over through the whole next JRH – until the next JRH scheduled for Sep. 22nd & 23rd, 2025); "G-D's Physics" therefore also predicted a further (singular) MAI increase in the rate of the universe's expansion beginning from these two (prospective) days of the past JRH (Sep. 22nd & 23rd, 2025) of another $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ increase in the universe's expansion rate (e.g., that will carry through the whole next JRH)!

B. Longitudinal measurement of the (same) UNCIARE-JRH's cumulative MAI's – across any given time-span! A second manner of testing (and validating) G-D's Physics UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction could be experimentally tested at particularly set "time-points", e.g., for instance: a) Before 10 years (e.g., 2014 after the JRH of 2014): a predicted $10 \times \text{MAI} = 10 \times \text{MAI}$ of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ "decrease" from the current Hubble's constant, i.e., ; b) Before 50 years (e.g., (e.g., 2014 after the JRH of 2014): a predicted $10 \times \text{MAI} = 50 \times \text{MAI}$ of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ decrease from the current Hubble's constant, c) Before 100 years : a predicted $100 \times \text{MAI} = \text{MAI}$ of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ decrease from the current Hubble's constant.

C. "G-D's Physics Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances": regards a comparison of an Accelerator's precise measurements of the significantly greater number of times that such a ("more massive") Muon particle would appear across a given series of UF's frames(i.e., or in fact a certain measurable sample thereof!) than the "less-massive" electron particle!

"G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" (unique) "Critical Prediction", e.g., regarding the significantly smaller number of FTM's in which the 'electron' particle would be detected relative to the number of (such) FTM's in which the 'Muon' may be measured – needs to be corrected for the known subatomic (quantum theory related) "bias" towards the measurement of such 'more-massive' 'Muon' particle, relative to the measurements of a 'less massive' 'electron' particle; In other words "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" "Critical Prediction" regarding the significantly greater FTM's at which the 'more massive' Muon particle (M) would be detected, relative to the number of (equivalent) FTM's at which the 'less-massive' electron (e) particle would be detected should subtract

the "quantum measurement bias" (QMB) towards a more 'sensitive temporal measurement' of more massive particle:

$$\text{FTM}(M) - \text{QMB} > \text{FTM}(e)$$

To the extent that this "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" "Critical Prediction" is empirically validated, then this would provide an (unequivocal validation for "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm: i.e., specifically, for its novel conception of the manner in which that singular higher-ordered UCP differentially computes "more massive" particles, relative "less massive particles" Submission deadline: June 18th, 2025.

Publication of a "Special Issue" entitled: "Results of JOURNAL international Contest for Validation of G-D's Physics' "Critical Predictions": May 16th, 2025.

JOURNAL's Scientific Contest Committee: The selection of the Five Winning Articles will be carried out by JOURNAL's Scientific Contest Committee, Chaired by Dr. Jehonathan Bentovish who is the "Father" of this New "G-D's Physics" Twenty-First Century's Scientific Paradigm.

Submissions (& Inquiries): to the INTERNATIONAL CONTEST FOR VALIDATION OF G-D'S PHYSICS' NEW TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY'S SCIENTIFIC PARADIGM'S "CRITICAL PREDICTIONS"! should be emailed directly to drbentwich@gmail.com

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